

eu-citizen.science

**The Platform for Sharing, Initiating and
Learning Citizen Science in Europe**

Deliverable 6.2

**Report on the project's communication and dissemination
activities**

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Abstract	The EU-Citizen.Science project has ended after 3 years. WP6 has based the implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy on the deliverable D6.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan . This deliverable (D6.2) reports on all the activities that have been undertaken during the project's lifespan by breaking down the different tools used, their strategy and implementation and their performances.
Keywords	Citizen Science, communication, Dissemination.

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary.....	9
a. About EU-Citizen.Science	9
b. Why this report?	9
c. Project indicators	11
2. Communication and dissemination tools.....	12
a. Website & platform.....	13
b. Newsletters	16
c. Press releases.....	20
d. Social media	21
e. Offline tools: project leaflets & materials	28
f. Local and European wide events and conferences.....	29
g. Final event	30
h. Citizen science workrooms	30
i. Additional materials.....	31
3. Summary and conclusions.....	33
4. Annexes	36
a. Annex 1: Breakdown of the dissemination audiences	36
b. Annex 2: Breakdown of the dissemination tools.....	38
c. Annex 3: List of the different types of blog articles published on the platform	39
d. Annex 4: List of projects involved in the newsletter	40
e. Annex 5: Example of a newsletter	41
f. Annex 6: Responses and analysis for communication needs.....	46
g. Annex 7: Communication kit.....	47
h. Annex 8: List of Press releases/mentions about the platform launch.....	63
i. Annex 9: Offline tools: project leaflets & materials	68
j. Annex 10: List of events.....	71
k. Annex 11: Final event programme.....	80
l. Annex 12: Workroom programme	83
m. Annex 13: Satisfactory responses workroom	85
n. Annex 14: Visual identity	87
o. Annex 15: List of the mini teasers	95

List of figures

Figure 1: Evolution of the number of subscribers to the newsletter	19
Figure 2 Illustration of a tweet where EU-Citizen.Science has been tagged.....	23
Figure 3 Evolution of the Twitter audience	24
Figure 4 Evolution of the Twitter figures: Impressions and Engagements.....	25
Figure 5 Evolution of the Facebook audience.....	26
Figure 6 Evolution of the Facebook figures: : Impressions and Engagements.....	26
Figure 7 Evolution of the Instagram audience	27
Figure 8 Screenshot of the video teaser	32
Figure 9 Screenshot of the project's final video.....	33

List of tables

Table 1 Comparison between key performance indicators and final results	12
Table 2 List of the 10 most read blog posts on EU-Citizen.Science	16
Table 3 List of the newsletters sent throughout the project's lifetime and their respective open rates.....	20
Table 4 Overview of the social media paid campaigns and their performances	28

Version Log

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0.1	07/12	Lucie Steigleder	Initial draft
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0.3	14/12	Lucie Steigleder (Ecsite)	Comments addressed and final sent to the coordinators.

Definitions and Acronyms (tbc)

CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
Data	Information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. The focus is on research data that is available in digital form. (European Commission, 2016)
Dataset	A grouping of data
Digital Curation	Selection, preservation, maintenance and archiving of electronically stored data
DMP	Data Management Plan
DS	Data Set
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association

FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
Metadata	A description of data
MoRRI	Monitoring the evolution and benefits of responsible research and innovation
Open Access	Access that is free to all and free of any restrictions
Open Data	Data that can be freely used, shared and built on by anyone for any purpose
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
PPSR	Public Participation in Scientific Research
Repository	A location in which data is stored or managed
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals

1. Executive Summary

a. About EU-Citizen.Science

EU-Citizen.Science is an EU-funded project that started in January 2019 and ended in December 2021. More than a study of the European citizen science landscape, the project's ambition was to build, fill, and promote a sustainable platform and mutual learning space providing different tools, best practice examples and relevant scientific outcomes in order to mainstream citizen science in Europe. EU-Citizen.Science had 5 main identified objectives:

1. Establish EU-Citizen.Science as the community hub for high-quality citizen science exchange and learning in Europe
2. Consolidate the citizen science knowledge base and celebrate outstanding practices and state of the art in citizen science in Europe.
3. Empower diverse stakeholders to become citizen scientists, start citizen science initiatives, and adopt citizen science approaches professionally.
4. Explore new pathways for participatory governance, by strengthening links between citizen science and policy making
5. Advance citizen science into the mainstream of public engagement, science communication and education.

The EU-Citizen.Science¹ platform, which was officially launched in 2020 and has been updated and improved several times since, represents the main achievement and product of the project. EU-Citizen.Science is also the source of other achievements such as the organisation of international events, the development and publication of different training modules filling the gap observed in the citizen science educational offer or the establishment of a long-term collaboration among the EU-funded citizen science projects.

Coordinated by Museum für Naturkunde (MfN) in Berlin, the EU-Citizen.Science project involved 14 partners and 9 third parties, representing 14 European Member States and a variety of stakeholders ranging from universities, NGOs, local authorities, CSOs and natural history museums, along with several other project supporters.

b. Purpose of this report

For a project of such a large scale, the communication and dissemination strategy was of particular importance. This document reports on the communication and dissemination activities that have been conducted in **WP6: Dissemination, Exploitation and Strategic communication** throughout the project's lifetime. It synthesises the work that has been carried out by the EU-Citizen.Science partners over the three years of the project to engage a wide audience in the project's activities, in the platform building as well as in citizen science in general.

¹ <https://eu-citizen.science/>

This document will highlight the tools used for the communication activities, the strategy that has been implemented for their utilisation and their results and performance of each in enabling the project to achieve the objectives set out in **D6.1 Communication and Dissemination plan**.

These communication and dissemination² objectives were:

- **Communication Objective 1:** Raise public awareness and ensure maximum visibility of EU-Citizen.Science's key objectives, activities and outcomes at a European and international level, in particular the online platform.
- **Communication Objective 2:** Announce and promote EU-Citizen.Science's training events, contributing to increasing their attendance and engagement potential.
- **Communication Objective 3:** Support the communication of the partners at the local and national level.
- **Communication Objective 4:** Promote EU research and create a Europe-wide and international infrastructure for citizen science.
- **Dissemination Objective 1:** Identify targets, messages, tools and channels for each target audience; build an adequate and effective communication and dissemination plan to ensure the best impact of project results.
- **Dissemination Objective 2:** Design a comprehensive set of communications materials (including a project logo) to establish a clear identity for the project and maximize its exposure.
- **Dissemination Objective 3:** Use the dissemination channels; participate in workshops, conferences and international/ EC meetings.
- **Dissemination Objective 4:** Ensure persistent and long-lasting visibility for the project activities and outcomes on a dedicated platform.

Beyond this, based on the bid submitted, and on the work of a core group of partners and the coordinator, deliverable **D6.1 Communication and Dissemination plan** had also identified 6 target audiences:

- The general public
- Academia

² The EC defines communication and dissemination as follows: **Communication:** "Communication on projects is a strategically planned process, which starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange; **Dissemination:** "The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium." (Scherer et al. 2018).

- Teachers and schools
- Policy makers
- Science journalists and science media
- Industry and SMEs

For each of these groups, WP6 had foreseen the use of different tools and activities as established in the dissemination plan. Each tool will have an impact on a selection of the abovementioned target groups, thus the combination of all the tools has allowed the project to reach the entire expected audience.

The EU-Citizen.Science project, due to the digital nature of its core activity, has not dramatically been impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic and most of the tasks have been conducted without major disruptions. Of course, the health situation and related sanitary restrictions have brought their share of challenges, but the consortium has successfully been able to find alternatives. Regarding communication and dissemination, WP6 has seized these changes as opportunities to rely more on online strategies for reaching out to a global audience. For example, as there has been no physical edition of the Ecsite conference in 2020 and 2021, an alternative had to be found regarding the organisation of the pre-conference workshop stated in the description of task 6.4. By moving to an online setting, EU-Citizen.Science has been able to open this activity to more participants (50 instead of 40 originally foreseen), and has also expanded its reach beyond the participation to the conference and the financial and organisational constraints that result from it. Moreover, an online format brings many opportunities for a wider reach, such as using hashtags on Twitter or publishing recordings of events that make them available over a longer period of time.

c. Project indicators

The project had identified a number of measurable indicators to assess the progress made on the communication and dissemination objectives.

The following list can give a quick idea of the project progress:

Tool	Indicator	Number reached (as of end of November 2021)
Digital platform (website, platform, social media, newsletter)	10.000 unique visitors at the end of the project along all the channels of the digital platform.	88872 unique visitors on all the channels of the digital platform ³ .
● Project platform	At least 4.000 users	9525 returning visitors
● Facebook	1.200 followers	1761 followers

³ The number of 88872 unique visitors includes 52187 unique visitors on the EU-Citizen.Science platform, 2168 page views on Facebook and 34517 profile visits on Twitter; unfortunately, this data is not available for Instagram.

• Twitter	2300 followers	4385 followers
• Instagram	520 followers	805 followers
• Press release and newsletter	400 recipients	783 subscribers
EU-Citizen.Science events at local and EU level	1,500 attendees	5309 attendees in total
Participation in external workshops, conferences and events	35 presentations	56 participations to workshops, conferences and trade fairs.
Publications in journals and sector specific magazines	10 publications	11 publications ⁴
Final event	150 people attending	274 attendees

Table 1 Comparison between key performance indicators and final results

Overall, the total target number have been vastly exceeded.

2. Communication and dissemination tools

At the beginning of the project, and as described in D6.1, a number of tools have been selected to be implemented for the communication and dissemination strategy.

- a) Website & platform
- b) Newsletters
- c) Press releases
- d) Social media channels
- e) Project leaflets
- f) Local and European-wide events and conferences where the project has been presented
- g) Final event

Over the course of the project, additional opportunities have been identified and new tools have been integrated within our communication strategy:

- h) Citizen science workrooms
- i) Additional materials

The following section describes each of the tools, their objectives and implementation, and their performances. A more detailed breakdown of the communication and dissemination figures can be found in Annex 2.

⁴ The list of publications is available in Annex 1

a. Website & platform

Objectives

The EU-Citizen.Science platform was at the heart of the project's activities, and its design and implementation were coordinated by the **WP2 Platform, Community and Network Building**.

Prior to the official launch of the platform on the 6th of April 2020, the project's digital presence was ensured by a static website (Wordpress), which presented the project's aims and activities. The "Blog" and "Events" sections were dynamic, with regular articles published around project's progress as well as generic news from the citizen science landscape. This website was managed by Ecsite with the help of IberCivis and ECSA.

After the official launch of the platform, in addition to the different features developed within the scope of WP2, the "Blog"⁵ and "Events"⁶ sections were maintained and remained operational.

Strategy

The website and platform have been used as the central point, gathering all the pieces of information published around the project. The other tools, such as the newsletter or the social media channels, were vectors of the information presented on the website and were often inviting their audience to visit the platform.

Three partners had publisher and administrator status on the website and the platform: IberCivis, ECSA, and Ecsite.

The "Events" section was powered by the "publication team" which collected all activities and events of interest for the citizen science community. Relevant information such as the date of the event, location, target audience and a short description was presented.

The "News" section is without a doubt the most diverse tool, as well as the most exhaustive about the project. Different sorts of articles have been published (Links to the following articles can be found in Annex 3):

- Updates about the project activities and progress: As the project moved forward, more and more activities were organised or outcomes were published. For example, the open call for training modules developed within **WP5 Training needs assessment, creation and delivery** was fully explained on a specific page of the website⁷, and the dedicated blog article related the main points and pointed out to this page.

⁵ <https://eu-citizen.science/blog>

⁶ <https://eu-citizen.science/events>

⁷ <https://eu-citizen.science/call/>

- Newsletters: Newsletters will be further described in the dedicated section of this deliverable (2.b, page 16). Each newsletter edition included several elements: one or several main articles, news from other projects or EU-Citizen.Science updates, which were all published as a separate article on the blog. A more global article, announcing the campaign and explaining the topic of the newsletter, was also produced.

- Updates from other citizen science projects or initiatives: As the EU-Citizen.Science motto is “by the community, for the community”, the blog section was naturally available for everyone – even from outside of the project) wanting to share their activities or updates, related to citizen science. This was the occasion to strengthen the relationship and collaboration with the different SWAFS⁸ project (in addition to their participation to the newsletter, as described in the section 2.b, page 16), but other citizen science projects, at a more local scale, were also invited to get involved. This opportunity will be kept open after the end of the project with the introduction of a news “submission form”.

- Specific and time-relevant publications: It has always been crucial for the EU-Citizen.Science communication to be up to date with world events, even when not directly related to the citizen science field. For example, when the COVID-19 crisis started, the consortium reacted rapidly by publishing a list of projects that can be done at home. On a brighter note, the summer 2021 has been the occasion to share a selection of projects and resources that can be done during summertime.

- Information shared by partners: Alongside EU-Citizen.Science, most of the consortium partners were also involved in other projects or initiatives related to citizen science. For example, IberCivis was involved in the organisation of a webinar presenting a report on the situation of citizen science in Spain, some of these activities could be of interest for our platform audience.

⁸ SWAFS: Science with and for Society (SwafS) in Horizon 2020 - <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/science-and-society>

- A selection of relevant events: Many international events linked with citizen science have been taking place throughout the 3 years of the projects. They were usually featured in the “Events” section of the platform, but some of them were also the object of dedicated blog posts, based on their relevance and quality.
- Opinion pieces sharing the project’s position on certain matters: The blog articles describing the project’s updates were not always very detailed about the decisions behind these changes or about the rationale behind our activities. For the sake of openness and transparency, partners had the opportunity to publish articles to go further into these topics. For example, the fact that the code for the EU-Citizen.Science platform has been stored for posterity as part of the GitHub Archive Program, in the Arctic Code Vault.
- Relevant deliverables: Some of the public deliverables published by the project were worth sharing with the global citizen science community, when they tackle topics that are relevant to the whole field.
- Opportunities: sharing opportunities such as job opportunities or call for proposals was essential to ensure that the platform and the EU-Citizen.Science communication in general could be useful to users.

eu-citizen.science, Oct 14, 2020, 8:27 a.m.
A decade of Citizen Science (2020-2030) in support of the SDGs
 Noted an international event dedicated to the link between Citizen Science and the Sustainable Development Goals.

eu-citizen.science, Oct 15, 2020, 10:02 a.m.
The EU-Citizen.Science platform is part of the GitHub Archive Program
 The EU-Citizen.Science platform will be stored for posterity as part of the GitHub Archive Program, in the Arctic Code Vault.

eu-citizen.science, March 25, 2020, 12:26 p.m.
Citizen Science Training Needs & Resources
 This is the first survey from the EU-Citizen.Science project, which aims to create a global Citizen Science platform that features custom-made training modules that address community needs.

eu-citizen.science, Feb 19, 2021, 1:57 p.m.
Job opportunity at ECSA - citizen science project officer
 We post an exciting professional opportunity for the benefit of the citizens science movement in Europe. This role is an exciting opportunity for a citizen science specialist to work on two projects at the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA).

Performances

During the period between 7 April 2020 to 30 November 2021, the Events page reached a total of 4895 page views and is the 5th most consulted page on the website

During the same period, the blog page (that lists all the blog article published on the platform) gathered a total of 3929 page views, which puts it at the 12th position of the most visited pages.

In total, 110 blog posts have been published over the three years of the project. All together, they have gathered more than 5642 page views.

Table 2 shows the most read blog articles on the EU-Citizen.Science platform, and their respective page views.

Topic	Page Views	Type of blog article
Publication of ECSA's Characteristics of Citizen Science	360	Update about the project's activities
Call for collaboration to develop metadata guidelines for publishing citizen scientist datasets	211	Updates from other CS projects or initiatives
"Tips and tricks for Hosting a Successful Collaborative Online Meeting", presented by Cos4Cloud	206	Updates from other CS projects or initiatives
Citizen science resources related to the COVID19 pandemic	180	Specific and time-relevant publications
Supporting Environmental Democracy and the Aarhus Convention - ECSA Comments	171	Information shared by partners
#MonthOfTheProjects initiative on EU-Citizen.Science	165	Updates about the project activities and progress
Public report: best methods in citizen science engagement published by CSI-COP	148	Updates from other CS projects or initiatives
Publication of D7.1 - Evaluation and impact framework	141	Relevant deliverables
Call for proposals: training modules	137	Update about the project's activities
Pan-European citizen science initiative 'Looking for Cowslips'	131	Updates from other CS projects or initiatives

Table 2 List of the 10 most read blog posts on EU-Citizen.Science

b. Newsletters

Objectives

The initial format of the EU-Citizen.Science newsletter, as described in the Description of Action, was rather standard and was supposed to share project's updates with contribution from all partners. Very early on in the project, MfN and Ecsite reached out to the four other SWAFS projects linked with citizen science that started at a similar time, and invited them to take part in a collaborative initiative. The idea behind this joint newsletter on citizen science was to enable EU-Citizen.Science and the other SWAFS projects involved to liaise together and contribute to strengthening the ties of the European citizen science community.

Therefore, the new format of the citizen science newsletter had the following objectives:

- Allowing all projects involved to share and disseminate their updates to a wider public, by benefiting from each project's audiences.
- Strengthening the collaboration initiated by Task **T1.5, Cooperation with RIA projects and other EU-funded projects** and fostering synergies among the projects.
- Creating and offering a service that enables subscribers to get regular updates about the citizen science field while being offered food for thought on issues that are relevant to the citizen science community.

Strategy and implementation

The newsletter has been designed, built and sent out via the Mailchimp platform. The coordination, design and management of the newsletter have been carried out by Ecsite, in collaboration with other partners and with contributions from the other projects.

The first newsletter was released in June 2019 and featured four other projects. Over the course of the EU-Citizen.Science project, this number has grown steadily to reach the number of 19 projects participating in at least one issue of our newsletter (all editions combined, including the final one scheduled for January). The list of projects involved can be found in Annex 4.

Most of the editions focused on a specific topic, which was either particularly relevant in terms of timing, or related to current events, or of general interest to citizen science enthusiasts. In that case, the newsletters were based on the following structure:

- One main article would explore this topic in depth, usually an interview of an expert coming from a different field (not necessarily a citizen science practitioner), in order to bring an external perspective of the topic that can then be applied to citizen science. The interviews being generally too long to be featured in an email campaign, it was first published on the website as a resource and only the first questions or paragraphs were included in the newsletter. Readers were then incited to visit the website to have access to the full article.
- Each project collaborating on the newsletter had two possibilities to contribute to the editions. They could either express their own view on the topic with a short piece or share a newsworthy update about their project's progress, not necessarily linked to the topic of this edition.
- A specific section was reserved for important updates about EU-Citizen.Science, events where the project was presented, publications of deliverables or any important news about the project.
- The newsletter ended with a list of events related to citizen science.

An example of a newsletter can be found in Annex 5.

At the beginning, as the initiative only involved a few projects, the communication and coordination between the involved projects was mostly carried out via emails, but regular meetings were organised with all participants to decide on the future subjects. As more and more projects joined the newsletter, the communication took place entirely by emails. The topics were

commonly decided using voting tools such as google form or doodle, following suggestions from Ecsite or ideas proposed by the participating projects. Sometimes, when the release of the newsletter coincided with a large-scale event (such as the Citizen Science and SDGs conference organised in Berlin in October 2020) or global situations impacting the citizen science field (such as the COVID-19 pandemic), these subjects were naturally chosen.

With the growing number of projects involved, a specific process has been put in place to select the most relevant contributions. Indeed, to ensure the quality and maintain the newsletter to a reasonable size, no more than 4-5 contributions were accepted per section. The collaborating projects were invited to apply through a google form and send a short pitch describing the piece they wanted to submit. Ecsite was in charge of selecting the contributions, by basing their choice on the relevance and time-concordance of the submissions. A particular attention was given to having a fair rotation and to assuring that every project was regularly featured.

A number of newsletters were dedicated to particular events or activities revolving around the project EU-Citizen.Science. Especially towards the end of the project, when such announcements were more frequent. These editions were shorter and more monotopic than the “classical” ones.

Performances

At the time of writing this deliverable, the EU-Citizen.Science newsletter had an audience of 783 subscribers, which is a result that is rarely reached by EU projects.

Two aspects might explain this success:

- Collaboration with many projects. This joint newsletter was based on the synergy between the different EU projects that each had a different target audience, based on their core topic. The newsletter has greatly benefited from this extended reach.
- The newsletter was not only reporting on the project activities but also offering quality content to the readers. The added value of producing interviews or articles made it possible to attract subscribers that were not especially interested in the project's updates, but in citizen science in general.

Figure 1: Evolution of the number of subscribers to the newsletter

The figure 1 shows the evolution of the number of subscribers to the citizen science joint newsletter. The pink vertical bars indicate the release of the different campaigns (described in the table 1 below). As we can see, regular promotion campaigns inviting people to subscribe to our newsletter were conducted, which resulted in increases prior to the publication dates.

The overall number of subscribers has evolved gradually throughout the three years of the project.

As of December 2021, 12 newsletters have been sent in total. The final edition is currently in preparation and will be released in January 2022.

No	Topic	Date	Number of subscribers	Open rate (%)	Open rate (Number)
#1	Presentation of the project and of the newsletter	Jun-19	87	73,6	64
#2	Air pollution	Oct-19	298	45,6	136
#3	Inclusion	Feb-20	401	52,6	211
#4	Launch of the platform	Apr-20	467	65,2	304
#5	COVID-19 pandemic	Jul-20	565	38,7	217
#6	First platform update: community forums, training resources and institutional profiles	Sep-20	600	49,7	296
#7	Citizen science and the SDGs	Nov-20	647	48,8	313
#8	Second platform update: Training modules and Moodle integration	Jan-21	675	48	321
#9	Call for cascading grants	Mar-21	689	51,9	355
#10	Policy Event	Jun-21	730	44,2	318
#11	Citizen science workrooms	Jun-21	730	41,3	298

#12	EU-Citizen.Science and ACTION final conference	Nov-21	777	48,2	367
#13	End of the EU-Citizen.Science project: Upcoming activities and outcomes from all the citizen science projects.	Jan-22	-	-	-

Table 3 List of the newsletters sent throughout the project's lifetime and their respective open rates

The table 3 shows the success rates of the different editions. As the number of subscribers has been continuously rising, the open rate has been pretty irregular. The dates of the publications (and their correspondence to holiday periods for example) definitively had an impact, as the lowest open rate corresponds to the newsletter that has been sent in the middle of the summer.

c. Press releases

Objectives

The deliverable **D6.1 Communication and dissemination plan** mentioned press releases as a tool to “inform on the project milestones and main results and to get some press coverage on the project activities in order to attract science communicators and science bloggers.”

Strategy and implementation

The strategy has slightly shifted from the original plan. The next paragraphs will describe what has been prepared for the official launch of the platform, as this event was heavily promoted compared to the other ones. For the other milestones, the communication process was similar, but to a lesser extent.

Prior to the first milestone of the project (the official launch of the platform in April 2020), partners had been invited to fill in a form and express their needs in terms of communication. The idea was to identify which material they would be more likely to use, and for which audience. The 17 responses have indicated that rather than press releases, partners would be more willing to use a factsheet, social media posts and a video. The principal audiences that they wanted to target with these materials were the general public, the press, academia, policymakers and educators. The complete analysis of this survey can be found in Annex 6.

Therefore, instead of producing a press release, Ecsite developed a “communication kit” that included:

- Two factsheets (one aimed at the general public and another one for policymakers)
- An email template that partners could use to send to their personal contacts
- An article to be published on institutional websites
- Pictures to be used during the campaign
- Social media posts.

The video has been produced later in May, and will be further described in the section 2.i Other materials (page 31).

A guideline document explaining the different steps and how to use the materials was included. The kit (Annex 7) has been made available to all partners on the google drive in advance to let them the time to translate the materials in their local language.

Performances

This multi-channel approach has been very successful and has allowed the platform to benefit from a large media coverage.

In total, 22 articles have been published about the launch of the platform (from consortium partners and from external organisations), 12 additional mentioned the platform among other of the project's activities. Regarding social media, 15 Facebook posts and a significant number of tweets have been dedicated to promoting the launch.⁹ The list of all the publications can be found in Annex 8.

d. Social media

Objectives

EU-Citizen.Science inherited Doing It Together Science's (DITOs)¹⁰ Twitter¹¹, Facebook¹², and Instagram¹³ accounts at the end of May 2019. This social media handover was coordinated by Ecsite with the UCL team managing DITOs communications package. Since 31 May 2019, the three social media inherited from DITOs were officially ensuring EU-Citizen.Science's online presence and have been used to communicate and disseminate project results, trainings, surveys, etc. The target audience for this tool was a public that is already interested in citizen science, but efforts were made to expand this audience and attract newcomers to the field.

Strategy & implementation

As the three channels don't necessarily have the same type of users and don't emphasise on the same kind of content, they have been utilised in different manners and will later be described separately.

Time-wise, our social media strategy has been split in two periods:

- Prior to the launch of the platform, most of the project's activities were internal and oriented towards the platform production. There were only few updates to share or materials to promote on social media. This phase has therefore been used to establish the

⁹ A list gathering all the tweets about the platform launch can be accessed at this link

<https://twitter.com/EUCitSciProject/timelines/1250018994767224833>

¹⁰ <http://togetherscience.eu/blog/from-doing-it-together-science-to-eu-cit-sci-passing-along-our-social-media-accounts>

¹¹ <https://twitter.com/EUCitSciProject>

¹² <https://www.facebook.com/EUCitSciProject/>

¹³ <https://www.instagram.com/eucitsciproject/>

project's brand within the citizen science community, and increase the project's visibility. This has been achieved by sharing on twitter (and to a lesser extent on Facebook and Instagram) general news and articles about the citizen science field, promoting interesting projects and /or sharing resources of interests.

- After the launch of the platform, the three channels have been actively used to promote and disseminate the many features present on the platform as well as those added over the different platform releases. In the second period of the project, the consortium has also had the occasion to create and/or disseminate more outcomes (such as organising events, publications of deliverables of interest for the whole community etc). These elements have given materials to the social media channels.

Performance

There are many ways metrics can be evaluated for social media. As no paid platform was used to gather deep data on the social media accounts, the free analytics tools for each platform were used to measure social media success, where follower count, impressions¹⁴, engagement¹⁵ and profile visits have been analysed. Instagram's analytics functions are limited so only follower count have been displayed.

Overall, the project's social media channels have been a strong communication and dissemination tool, and many factors indicate that EU-Citizen.Science was recognised as well-known and influential source of news in the field of citizen science. For example, the twitter account has been frequently tagged in external publications, notably from the European commission.

¹⁴ Impressions: The number of times a post entered a person's screen

¹⁵ Engagement: The number of times a someone interacts with a post (by commenting, liking, sharing or clicking upon particular elements of the post).

Figure 2 Illustration of a tweet where EU-Citizen.Science has been tagged

Moreover, user-generated tools that are listing influential accounts based on hashtags uses¹⁶ regularly named EU-Citizen.Science as one of the most active accounts using the #CitizenScience hashtag.

- Twitter

Key metrics

Final number of followers	4385
Number of posts	659
Page visits	34517

Without any doubt, Twitter has been EU-Citizen.Science's most active platform. With more than 650 tweets, this platform has not only been used to promote the project's activities, but also to share news and raise awareness about the citizen science field in general. Twitter particularities, such as only allowing concise texts and granting a really short lifespan to each post, made this platform the place to quickly react to news or events in the field.

Twitter has also been the most "informal" platform. As it is common practice, Twitter gives the opportunity to use a more casual tone and visual elements such as gifs, to emphasise an emotion or to simply illustrate a post when no picture was available.

¹⁶ such as NODE graph gallery (<https://nodexlgraphgallery.org/Pages/Default.aspx?search=%22citizenscience%22>), a project from the Social media research foundation (<https://www.smrfoundation.org/>)

Generally speaking, Twitter gave EU-Citizen.Science many occasions to interact with other accounts, with retweets, likes or replies, and then consolidate the relations and synergies with other projects or other citizen science actors.

The pace of publication has varied, with regular peaks during events that were highly promoted or live-tweeted. In a regular setting, EU-Citizen.Science posted 2-3 tweets per week.

The following figures cover the period from 31 May 2019 (launch of the project’s social media channels) to 30 November 2021 (date of writing of this deliverable).

Figure 3 Evolution of the Twitter audience

Regarding the audience, the DITOs project had transmitted to EU-Citizen.Science a solid account that was already well-established in the digital landscape with more than 1500 followers. Since the handover, growth has been constant. A peak can be observed in April 2020, which corresponds to the official launch of the platform. A similar observation can be made on in January 2021, for the second update of the platform.

Evolution of the Twitter figures

Figure 4 Evolution of the Twitter figures: Impressions and Engagements

When looking at the success of the posts published on the EU-Citizen.Science account, the average engagement rate and impressions rate seem to follow a common pattern that has been influenced by the milestones of the project, as seen in the figure 3.

- Facebook

Key metrics

Final number of followers	1761
Number of posts	129
Page visits	2168

Facebook has been used to share important updates about the project or the important news in the citizen science field. But, contrarily to Twitter, the posts did not have this dimension of immediacy and were more substantiated, as Facebook allows for longer texts. Unlike Twitter, Facebook does not offer such easy to use visual help such as gifs to illustrate a post. The use of pictures to accompany the post was then more carefully thought out.

Facebook had about 1-2 posts per week.

The following insights are covering the period from February 2020 to November 2021, as Facebook only provides data for this limited period.

Figure 5 Evolution of the Facebook audience

Figure 4 illustrates the evolution of the followers' number of the EU-Citizen.Science Facebook page. Similar to Twitter, the launch of the platform has led to a significant growth in the project's audience.

Evolution of the Facebook figures

Figure 6 Evolution of the Facebook figures.

As it is clearly visible in figure 5, the Facebook posts about the platform launch have been extremely successful. As mentioned before, Facebook has not been as strong as Twitter in terms of reach, and it has not been EU-Citizen.Science priority for the promotion of the project's milestones (platform updates for example). The data is more sensitive to variations, and it only takes a couple of successful posts in a row to create a pick in the graphic, which is what has been the case in April 2020.

- Instagram

Key metrics

Final number of followers	805
Number of posts	95

Figure 7 Evolution of the Instagram audience

In terms of insights, unfortunately Instagram does not give the possibility to export the data in the same way as Facebook and Twitter, as this feature is only available with paid online tools. As quantitative data, the only insight available is a fragmented evolution of the number of followers, whose numbers have been gathered at several occasions (for presentations or project meetings). Although this graphic does not reflect the exact reality, similar to what has been for the other channels, the launch of the platform in April 2020 has brought many followers to the EU-Citizen.Science social media accounts.

Paid campaigns

As social media have been one of the strongest channels used by EU-Citizen.Science, and they are massively used by the global citizen science community, they represented a great opportunity for the project to disseminate its products and activities. The EU-Citizen.Science platform, as well as the other project's outcomes, can be useful for a wide group of citizen science, that goes beyond the number of people subscribed to the project's social media channels. Which is why it has been decided early on the project, in order to reach the widest audience possible, to invest some of the budget into social media paid campaigns.

In total, 5 paid campaigns have been conducted over the lifespan of the project. They were mostly used to promote EU-Citizen.Science outputs, more than just sharing updates on the project's progresses.

Facebook and Twitter have been the two preferred platforms, as Instagram's functions were less developed. It is also important to mention that Facebook and Twitter's strategies for paid ads have evolved over the project's lifespan, with for example the possibility to choose an objective for the campaign (What is the priority: to get more people seeing the ad or to get more people clicking on the link?). Therefore, some pieces of information (such as click numbers) are not available for each campaign and the results can appear very different from one campaign to another, because they have been built and were displayed differently.

The table 4 below shows an overview of the campaigns conducted over the 3 years of the project, and their respective performances.

Occasions	Date	Platform	Impressions	Clicks	Duration of the campaign (days)	Success (Number of impressions per day)
Launch of the platform	Apr-20	Facebook	35104	-	5	7021
		Twitter	24443	134	5	4889
Second update of the platform	Jan-21	Facebook	29670	578	5	5934
		Twitter	28780	-	5	5756
Policy Event	Jun-21	Facebook	47494	251	5	9499
		Twitter	102709	7292	5	20542
"What's new in citizen science?" - Final platform update	Oct-21	Facebook	187530	937	20	9377
		Twitter	243887	1033	20	12194
"The future of citizen science" Final conference	Nov-21	Facebook	193550	956	14	13825
		Twitter	229669	800	14	16405

Table 4 Overview of the social media paid campaigns and their performances

e. Offline tools: project leaflets & materials

Objectives

Promotional materials following the graphic identity templates, design guidelines, and fact sheet have been produced for the partners to present and promote EU-Citizen.Science.

With the impact that the COVID-19 pandemic has had on physical events, most of these materials have been adapted to an online setting. The very few printed materials produced by the project have been designed on a case-basis, when a particular event requested a specific format.

The “Performances” section of these items will not be presented as there is no data regarding these static elements.

Strategy and implementation.

A number of materials has been produced by MfN or IberCivis, and can be consulted in Annex 9.

- Poster

IberCivis has been of great help in producing such materials, and notably a promotional poster in different format. This poster was aimed at presenting the different features and opportunities offered by the platform, in an engaging and simple medium. The poster has been updated several times, following the introduction of new features on the platform.

- Postcard

For the few onsite events that have been happening over the course of the project and at which EU-Citizen.Science was presented, some merchandises have been produced in order to grab the attendees’ attention and if possible be brought home by them.

In this regard, a postcard with the EU-Citizen.Science logo has been produced: it was given to visitors for free, and they were invited to use it to send to one of their contacts.

- Project’s roadmap

In order to help describing the project for digital presentations, a roadmap has been produced by IberCivis, listing the main steps and milestones of the project.

- Rollup and poster

A rollup and a poster have been designed to decorate booths or stands at physical events.

f. Local and European wide events and conferences

Objectives

The objectives were to present EU-Citizen.Science at events and conferences that are related to citizen science. Throughout the project, these events and conferences have contributed to raising awareness of citizen science and the project.

Strategy, implementation & performances

Over the project’s lifetime, a total of 94 events including conferences, workshops and other events were attended or organised by consortium partners. These events collectively reached a total of 11275 people from a mix of stakeholder groups. This is a successful achievement in light of the COVID-19-pandemic which caused many conferences and events to be cancelled.

The list of events that have been attended by the consortium can be found in Annex 10.

g. Final event

Objectives

The EU-Citizen.Science final event was an opportunity to celebrate the achievements of the project as well as disseminate the results towards different stakeholders. It was stated in the communication and dissemination plan that “Led by MfN, the final meeting and final event of the project will take place in Brussels. It will be hosted by Ecsite’s Linked Third Party RBINS in December 2021”.

Unfortunately, due to the current health situation and related risks and restrictions measures, it has been decided, in agreement with the project officer, that the final event would be organised online.

Strategy and implementation

In addition to the switch to an online setting, another significant change has been operated on the final event: it has been organised in collaboration with the ACTION project. It has been decided to join forces with this other SWAFS project that is also ending in order to offer a more diverse program and attract more participants interested by the synergies created by this partnership.

The event took place on 24 and 25 November 2021 with the title **The future of citizen science: sharing experiences from the European community** and was described as a “gathering of the global citizen science community full of exciting talks, sharing of experiences, stimulating debates and informal networking moments”. It was followed by a Satellite high-level policy event.

The programme can be available on the Annex 11.

The utilisation of the platform “Hopin” allowed to organise, besides the presentations and interactive sessions, a few networking moments as well as a booth exhibition where the other SWAFS projects were invited to present their projects.

Performances

In total, more than 400 participants registered for the event, and 274 actually attended over the two days. Participation reached a peak around 153 attendees online at the same time.

h. Citizen science workrooms

Objectives

One of the main activities described in T6.4 was the organisation of a “pre-conference workshop at one of Ecsite’s Annual Conferences, either in 2020 or 2021”. Unfortunately, the current health situation has forced the majority of events to move online, the Ecsite conference was no exception to this rule. For the 2021 edition of the Ecsite conference, the “pre-conference” format has been rethought and adapted to the online setting. This change has been done with the agreement of the project officer.

This new format was called a workroom, “a short series of online talks, group discussions and workshops, and even some offline preparation, all centred around one specific theme; an opportunity for participants to broaden knowledge together”.

Strategy and implementation

The EU-Citizen.Science workroom has been internally organised by a “workroom taskforce” composed of partners from Ecsite, ECSA, MfN, RBINS, MFCR and FGC. The theme “Citizen science clinic: impact of citizen science” has been selected. The programme can be found in Annex 12.

The workroom took place in June and July 2021, with three consecutive sessions:

- 21/06: Inspiring stories
- 29/06: Impact assessment framework
- 06/07: Financial sustainability

Performances

The expected audience was citizen science practitioners or museums practitioners with a basic knowledge or experience in citizen science. Only 50 participation spots were available as the format of the sessions included workshops and interactive activities. However, for the sake of inclusivity and open-knowledge, the plenary presentations of each sessions were broadcasted on YouTube, and will stay available on the Ecsite’s YouTube channel.

In total, 12 speakers have been contributing and an average of 34 participants have attended each session (40+ for the first two sessions and 20+ for the third one, that took place at the beginning of July 2021)

A feedback form has been sent to the participants after the last workshop, 14 attendees have sent their responses. The results can be found in Annex 13. The strongest points of the workroom have been that participants found it **Interesting, Well presented** and they received **enough information during the workroom**. In the qualitative part of the survey, respondents shared that they particularly enjoyed the interactive activities, and for further editions they suggested to have more time dedicated to discussions.

i. Additional materials

Visual identity:

The project’s visual identity has been developed at the very beginning of the project. Coordinated by Ecsite with the contribution from MfN, ECSA and IberCivis, the company “Multitude” based in Amsterdam was selected after an open call launched in March 2019. They have developed the whole visual identity of the project (Annex 14), namely:

- Different variations of the logo, with an animated version
- Colour palette and a police pack
- Templates (word, powerpoint, factsheet)

Videos

In addition to all the materials that were prepared throughout the project and that have been foreseen in the **D6.1 Communication and Dissemination plan**, several activities developed within the project have been an occasion to produce different types of videos.

- Platform teasers and micro-teasers

As mentioned in the section Press releases (2.c page 20), a teaser video has been produced by ECSA to accompany the launch of the platform and present the different features available.

Figure 8 Screenshot of the video teaser

The video has been produced in English, and each of the partners has been invited to translate the script into their local language.

As many of the materials produced throughout the project, this video has been adapted to the new features developed. The latest version of the video teaser is available on the ECSA YouTube channel¹⁷.

Following the same design, 8 micro-teasers have been produced, each explaining one action that can be done on the platform. These short videos (less than 40s each) had the principal ambition to be used on social media and to incite users to interact with the platform. The list of these videos is available in Annex 15.

- Video of online events

Many of the events organised by EU-Citizen.Science have been recorded, and the videos have been made available online.

- Citizen science workrooms (21 June, 29 June and 6 July)¹⁸
- Citizen science for policy across Europe: (22 June 2021)¹⁹

¹⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hfPn85aupcU&list=PLB6IBD9OG9pD6OLR2cPVAjYEUmftsW98N&index=2>

¹⁸ https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLBzoZUncZNyaE-9HesraKjWFG_tMbWYRb

¹⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ufUe7GtSYqE>

- What's new in citizen science training: from open science to public engagement (27 Oct 2021)²⁰
- Final video

In order to celebrate the project's achievements and assure their legacy, Ecsite has produced a final video describing the different activities undertaken in the past three years. Going beyond the platform, the video underlines the collaborations that the project has created, the partnerships with the other SWAFS projects as well as main milestones: the publication of the ECSA's characteristics of citizen science²¹ or the "Citizen science for policy across Europe event"²².

Figure 9 Screenshot of the project's final video

This video has been published on the ECSA YouTube Channel²³ at the end of November 2021, and has also been used alongside the communication and promotion of the final event.

3. Summary and conclusions

²⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ISQMDHGA9KU>

²¹ Haklay, Muki, Motion, Alice, Balázs, Bálint, Kieslinger, Barbara, Greshake Tzovaras, Bastian, Nold, Christian, Dörler, Daniel, Fraisl, Dilek, Riemenschneider, Dorte, Heigl, Florian, Brounéus, Frederik, Hager, Gerid, Heuer, Katja, Wagenknecht, Katherin, Vohland, Katrin, Shanley, Lea, Deveaux, Lionel, Ceccaroni, Luigi, Weißpflug, Maike, ... Wehn, Uta. (2020). ECSA's Characteristics of Citizen Science. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3758668>

²² https://eu-citizen.science/policy_maker_event_2021/

²³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PLqfOXX_TRg

a. Concluding remarks

The EU-Citizen.Science project had ambitious goals, targeting a diverse field, meaning that the project required an ambitious and diverse communication and dissemination strategy, utilising a mix of tools and methods that allowed us to communicate our diverse outputs. In the wake of a global COVID-19 pandemic, EU-Citizen.Science adapted by pivoting physical events to online events, changing how outputs from the project worked, and also navigating a new online space where online competition had never been more pronounced.

Overall, EU-Citizen.Science reached high engagement numbers across all communication and dissemination methods, surpassing our initial targets. By utilising a mix of online presence, external events, promotional materials and publications, the project has been able to establish its position within the community of like-minded professionals in citizen science. In the end, the success of a project cannot be measured by the strength of one organisation alone, and the impact of EU-Citizen.Science has been due to the willingness of the partners and third parties to spread the project's message to their communities and to exploit the results in their own organisations and practice (for more details of project impact, see **D7.3 - Final Impact Assessment Report**).

Over the course of three years many lessons have been learned, which may guidance for future projects working in a similar field, targeting a similar cohort of stakeholders:

1. *Collaboration with other EU projects addressing similar topics.* This collaboration initiated by Task **T1.5. Cooperation with RIA projects and other EU-funded projects** was a great benefit for the work undertaken within WP6. Indeed, mutual exchanges and help have allowed the initiatives produced by each project to gain momentum and to reach a wider audience than isolated EU-projects ever could. In addition, it has also enhanced and enriched the quality of the materials produced, the best example of this being the joint-newsletter.
2. *The power of the online citizen science community.* The citizen science community was already well established, and had already a strong digital presence, due to the collaboration and networking possibilities made available via a digital medium and many projects being available online. This presence has been one of the strongest strengths of the EU-Citizen.Science project, and has allowed it to not be dramatically impacted by the global COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, the enthusiasm of the community for any interactive activity has been greatly beneficial and appreciated for the events organised over the project's lifetime.
3. *Not starting from scratch.* The EU-Citizen.Science project had the enormous pleasure of inheriting the social media channels from the DITOs project, which has been of great help. Indeed, when launching social media channels, the first months are usually critical, and huge efforts have to be made to ensure that the channels reach potential subscribers. EU-Citizen.Science had the chance to start from an already-existing audience, which was willing to stay subscribed as the two projects had similar topics. Increasing an audience that is already established and significant is way easier than starting from zero, which,

coupled with the efforts that have been made throughout the project, explains the considerable success achieved by EU-Citizen.Science.

b. The future of EU-Citizen.Science channels

After its end, the majority of EU-Citizen.Science outputs will be transferred to ECSA, which agreed to manage the platform for the next 5 years. Social media channels, as well as the newsletter, will also be handed to ECSA after January 2021. They will be maintained and keep on updating the citizen science community about major news and events happening in the field.

4. Annexes

a. Annex 1: List of publications published over the 3 years of EU-Citizen.Science

- Hager, G., Kieslinger, B., Hecker, S., & Haklay, M. (2021). The characteristics of citizen science in a fishbowl. Proceedings of Austrian Citizen Science Conference 2020 — PoS(ACSC2020), 393, 024. <https://doi.org/10.22323/1.393.0024>
- Haklay, M. (2021). Why is it so difficult to integrate citizen science into practice? In K. Cohen & R. Doubleday (Eds.), In: Cohen, K and Doubleday, R, (eds.) Future directions for citizen science and public policy. (Pp. 108–116). Centre for Science and Policy: Cambridge, UK. (2021) (No. 11; Issue 11, pp. 108–116). Centre for Science and Policy. <https://www.csap.cam.ac.uk/media/uploads/files/1/future-directions-for-citizen-science-and-public-policy-web-v6.pdf>
- Haklay, M., Fraisl, D., Greshake Tzovaras, B., Hecker, S., Gold, M., Hager, G., Ceccaroni, L., Kieslinger, B., Wehn, U., Woods, S., Nold, C., Balázs, B., Mazzonetto, M., Ruefenacht, S., Shanley, L. A., Wagenknecht, K., Motion, A., Sforzi, A., Riemenschneider, D., ... Vohland, K. (n.d.). Contours of citizen science: A vignette study. Royal Society Open Science, 8(8), 202108. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.202108>
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- Roche, J., Bell, L., Galvão, C., Golumbic, Y. N., Kloetzer, L., Knoben, N., Laakso, M., Lorke, J., Mannion, G., Massetti, L., Mauchline, A., Pata, K., Ruck, A., Taraba, P., & Winter, S. (2020). Citizen Science, Education, and Learning: Challenges and Opportunities. Frontiers in Sociology, 5, 110. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsoc.2020.613814>
- Roche, J., Ni Shuilleabhain, A., Mooney, P., Barber, G. L., Bell, L., & Ryan, C. (2021). Citizen Science in Ireland. Frontiers in Communication, 6, 19. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2021.629065>

- Skarlatidou, A., & Haklay, M. (2021). Citizen science impact pathways for a positive contribution to public participation in science. *Journal of Science Communication*, 20(6), A02. <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.20060202>
- Skarzauskiene, A., & Mačiulienė, M. (2021). How to Build Sustainable Online Communities: Implications from Lithuania Urban Communities Case Study. *Sustainability*, 13(16), 9192. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13169192>
- Wagenknecht, K., Woods, T., Sanz, F. G., Gold, M., Bowser, A., Rüfenacht, S., Ceccaroni, L., & Piera, J. (2021). EU-Citizen.Science: A Platform for Mainstreaming Citizen Science and Open Science in Europe. *Data Intelligence*, 3(1), 136–149. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00085

b. Annex 2: Breakdown of the dissemination tools

Type of Activity	Number	Reach
Activities jointly with other EU projects	1	72
Brokerage event	1	30
Exhibition	5	21086
Organisation of Conference	11	4404
Organisation of Workshop	32	778
Other	14	3221
Participation to a conference	36	4683
Participation to a workshop	25	1253
Popularised publication (not peer-reviewed)	6	5639
Press-release	39	28118
Radio/TV	1	- ²⁴
Social Media	1196	4544952
Trade fair	2	30
Training	1	25
Video/film	16	1540
Website	71	5314

²⁴ Unfortunately, no estimation of the audience reach was available for this programme.

c. Annex 3: List of the different types of blog articles published on the platform

Type of blog articles	Example: title	Example: link
Updates about the project activities and progress	EU-Citizen.Science will fund 10 citizen science online training courses.	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2021/03/01/eu-citizenscience-will-fund-10-citizen-science-online-training-courses/
Newsletters description	Newsletter #5: Citizen Science and the SDGs	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2020/11/20/newsletter-5-citizen-science-and-sdgs/
Updates from other CS projects	Join the pan-European citizen science campaign!	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2021/02/19/join-pan-european-citizen-science-campaign/
Specific and time-relevant publications	Enjoy your citizen science summer: Seaside edition	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2021/08/10/enjoy-your-citizen-science-summer-seaside-edition/
Information shared by partners	Watch the presentation of the annual report on the situation of citizen science in Spain in 2019/2020.	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2020/12/15/watch-presentation-annual-report-situation-citizen-science-spain-20192020/
Relevant events	A decade of Citizen Science (2020-2030) in support of the SDGs	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2020/10/14/decade-citizen-science-2020-2030-support-sdgs/
Opinion pieces	The EU-Citizen.Science platform is part of the GitHub Archive Program	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2020/09/15/eu-citizenscience-platform-part-github-archive-program/
Relevant deliverables	Report in training needs	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2020/03/31/report-training-needs/
Opportunities	Job opportunity at ECSA – citizen science project officer	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2021/02/15/job-opportunity-ecsa-citizen-science-project-officer/

d. Annex 4: List of projects involved in the newsletter

Project's name	Website
ACTION	https://actionproject.eu
CitieS-Health	http://citieshealth.eu/
CoAct	https://coactproject.eu/
COESO	https://coeso.hypotheses.org/
Crowd4SDG	https://crowd4sdg.eu/
CSI-COP	https://csi-cop.eu/
CS-Track	https://cstrack.eu/
D-NOSES	https://dnoses.eu/
Envirocitizen	https://www.envirocitizen.eu/
FRANCIS	https://www.francis-project.eu/
INCENTIVE	https://incentive-project.eu/
MICS	https://mics.tools/
REINFORCE	https://www.reinforceeu.eu/
ROSiE	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006430
SEEDS	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006251
STEP-CHANGE	https://stepchangeproject.eu/
TIME4CS	https://www.time4cs.eu/
WeCount	https://www.we-count.net/
YouCount	https://www.youcountproject.eu/

e. Annex 5: Example of a newsletter

[View this email in your browser](#)

eu-citizen.science

Newsletter #3: Inclusion in citizen science

Are you reaching people beyond the typical white middle-class?

Dear reader,

After our last issue on [pollution](#), we chose to focus this third newsletter on a highly relevant topic for the science at large including citizen science: **Inclusion**.

This topic being so broad and diverse, we decided that one article wouldn't be enough to even start understanding what inclusion actually means and implies. This is why we are launching a whole **series of interviews**, to understand how inclusive is the citizen science field at the moment and how this situation could be improved.

We started by contacting **Emily Dawson**, Associate Professor in the Department of Science and Technology Studies at University College London. Her research focuses on science engagement with an emphasis on equity and social justice. She recently published the book "[Equity, Exclusion and Everyday Science Learning](#)".

Two other interviews are in the pipeline and will be published on the two following Mondays: **Taru Peltola**, associate professor of social sustainability at the Finnish Environment Institute and the University of West-Finland, author of the [Science for everybody? Bridging the socio-economic gap in urban biodiversity monitoring](#) #39 chapter, and **Shara Fisler**, founder of the [Ocean Discovery Institute](#) in San Diego, that is exclusively focusing on engaging young people from under-represented minorities.

But let's start from the beginning. Emily Dawson will share her reasons for why this fight against exclusion and inequality should be a priority in every science engagement initiative.

"Emily, We are curious to hear how your journey in equity and social justice related to science started."

When I started working in science museums, different initiatives were mentioning the notion of "engagement" and "new audiences". But in reality, everything was centred towards the typical "white, middle/upper class" public. After joining UWE (University of the West of England) in Bristol in 2006, we wanted to make our projects more inclusive, which ended up being harder than we had imagined. At the time, there was no literature or documentation available on this topic, apart from a single 2-page article. As I was frustrated by the lack of information on a subject that seemed so crucial to me, I decided to build the missing pieces of work myself and started a PhD.

"For me, doing science communication without being inclusive is pointless."

If we do so, we are agreeing to create things for people who already have what they need, and to exacerbating inequalities and the gap between privileged and under-privileged audiences.

"How would you define inclusion, and what are the first steps to work towards it?"

It seems extremely difficult to find a common definition of inclusion that fits everyone's idea, and it actually creates several problems. First, inclusion is nowadays a "hot topic" that is addressed in so many different contexts that it sometimes becomes meaningless.

"For instance, sadly, sometimes when a project or an organisation is working on a document about inclusion practices, the document itself becomes the intended work rather than the actual progress in the area, as we see in Sara Ahmed's work."

By being superficial, it undermines the whole process.

Then, some people tend to be rather "dogmatic" and only acknowledge their own definition of "inclusion", and refuse to accept the others. But inclusion and exclusion can take various forms and interpretations, which is why it should always be defined in a specific context and by having a conversation with people experiencing it.

We live in a complex society, where exclusion doesn't only have one social axis and people can experience more than one type of exclusion, often at the same time. At the moment, I find gender issues are often at the core of every discussion, but that can mean racism is overlooked. But, of course, it doesn't mean that racism is no longer present. The Black woman who worked with me experienced sexism alongside racism.(and other structural inequalities).

Even though it can be easier for institutions to create inclusive programmes focusing on one problem only, it would be of great value to think more broadly and start with what people actually experience in their everyday life (we could call this an intersectional approach).

Read the rest of the interview on our website:

Are you reaching people beyond the typical white middle-class?

Stay tuned! We'll publish the next interview already in one week [on our website](#) and promote it through our social media channels: [Twitter](#), [Facebook](#) and [Instagram](#).

In the meantime, have a look at [reflections on inclusion in citizen science from some of the ongoing EU-funded projects](#).

Updates from EU-Citizen.Science

Tick-tock... Last countdown before the launch of our platform

The flagship action of [our project](#), the design and implementation of a central platform for sharing knowledge, initiating action and supporting mutual learning, is at its final stage. Stay tuned, the platform will be launched in March!

In the meantime, we've been busy working on one of our most important deliverables, which lays the foundations for the whole project. If curious have a look at [Platform Functionality Requirements & Specification Report](#) which is looking the needs and requirements of our stakeholders and potential users.

The two core user groups of the EU-Citizen.Science Platform

Updates from our sister projects

ACTION, CiteS-Health, MICS and D-Noses are some of EU-Citizen.Science's sister projects. The beginning of the year has been a busy time for them with the accomplishment of various activities:

CitiesS-Health: Citizens education through participatory research learning

Preliminary results from the CitiesS-Health Barcelona pilot project activities helped to create a map of concerns in the different parts of the city.

ACTION

After the Open call of the ACTION project, six projects were selected and are ready to kick-off in a dedicated 3 day event starting on 17 February.

Measuring Impact of Citizen Science

Over the last months, MICS has developed a framework for measuring the impact of citizen science and organised co-design workshops.

D-NOSES

D-NOSES is kicking off a new pilot in Kampala, Uganda with the organisation of a conference and science education activities in 10 schools around the city.

REINFORCE is one of the new projects joining our newsletter.

New EU projects joining our newsletter!

From now on we will be relaying news from 10 EU citizen science projects. Carefully curated content will land in your inbox every 3 months. Meet some of the new citizen science projects that just started.

CoAct

[CoAct \(Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action\)](#) proposes a radically new approach to face four "wicked" social global issues by engaging vulnerable citizens acting as co-researchers.

CS Track

The aim of [CS Track \(Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action\)](#) is to broaden our knowledge about Citizen Science and the impact Citizen Science activities can have on individual citizens, organisations, and society.

REINFORCE

[REINFORCE \(Research Infrastructures FOR citizens in Europe\)](#) aims at creating a series of cutting-edge citizen science projects on frontier Physics research.

WeCount

[WeCount](#) aims to empower citizens to take a leading role in the production of data, evidence and knowledge around mobility in their own neighborhoods, and at street level.

Events for your diary:

April 2020: [Citizen Science Month](#)

24-26 May 2020: [ECSA 2020 conference](#) - Encounters in Citizen Science
- Our platform will be presented on Monday at 17:00 -

11-13 June 2020: [Ecsite Conference](#) - Echoes from the Future
- Join [our session](#) on Saturday at 14:30 -

24-26 June 2020: [9th Living Knowledge Conference](#) - Synergies in Research with and for Communities

30 June - 2 July 2020: [Final COST Action symposium](#) - Citizen Science: a scientific diamond?
- Our platform will be presented -

5-9 July 2020: [ESOF 2020 Euroscience Open Forum](#)

6-9 October 2020: [CitSciOz2020](#) Inspire, Impact, Influence

f. Annex 6: Responses and analysis for communication needs

Prior to the launch of the platform, partners were invited to express their needs and requirements for the communication of this milestones. They filled in a google form where they were asked to link the different audiences that they wanted to reach out to with the elements and materials that they would use.

The results are gathered in the following table. The most frequently given answers are highlighted in darker colours.

Which type of materials could be useful for your institution and for which target groups?

	General public	Press	academia	Policymakers	Educators	Industry	TOTAL
Factsheet	8	12	14	13	10	7	64
Press release template	4	11	4	5	4	2	30
Twitter	11	7	10	7	7	4	46
Facebook	13	4	8	5	9	5	44
Instagram	8	3	4	2	5	1	23
Video	12	7	11	9	10	6	55
Other	3	0	1	0	0	0	4
TOTAL	59	44	52	41	45	25	

g. Annex 7: Communication kit

The communication kit developed on the occasion of the launch of the platform includes:

1. Guidelines describing the communication strategy and the communication campaign
2. Textual factsheet for stakeholders
3. Visual factsheet for the general public
4. Template for personal emails
5. Template for article/blog to be published on the organisational website
6. Overview of the communication campaign on social media

I. Communication campain description

eu-citizen.science

Platform Launch Campaign

EU-Citizen.Science has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement no. 824580

Campaign goals

The primary goal of the campaign is to spread the news about the launch of the EU-Citizen.Science platform as far as possible reaching as many stakeholders as possible (academia, policy-makers, educators, citizen scientists), positioning the platform as the go-to-place for citizen science in Europe. The secondary goal of the campaign is to encourage the community to contribute Citizen Science Resources and Projects to the content of the platform.

Communication channels

Individual Emails

During the week of 6 - 10 April 2020 each member of the consortium, as well as the Third Parties, are asked to reach out to at least 10 individual contacts by email to let them know about the launch of the platform. You are welcome to use and adapt the email template provided.

Mailing Lists

ECSCA will send out the launch announcement in its newsletter and mailing list of members. Other lists to which the announcement will be sent:

- Ecsite Spokes magazine - Lucie to send
- ECSCA mailing list - Margaret to send
- CSA mailing list - Margaret to send
- BES mailing list - Margaret to send
- citsci mailing list - Margaret to send
- Share with CitSci Month folks - Margaret to send

Partners are asked to use their institutional mailing lists to share the news when possible.

Social media

A social media campaign is planned on Facebook, Twitter and Instagram. It contains two major items:

1. the social media countdown to the official launch of the platform which will take place from 01 to 6 April (each working day a new post will be issued with a fun fact about the platform).
2. on the day of the launch itself (6 April), a specific communication on social media

All partners need to make sure to share and like the posts across all platforms to ensure the largest impact possible. Please forward this guide to your institution's communications managers and ask them to support us via your channels. You are welcome to personalise the posts when sharing them e.g. mentioning your role in the platform creation.

Partners organisation websites

Please publish news on your organisational website about the launch of the platform to make sure your users are reached. A news item in English will be provided to be adapted or translated.

Newsletters

EU-Citizen.Science mailing list will be used to communicate the launch of the platform. Each partner is asked to take any opportunity of their institutional newsletters and mailing lists and make the announcement of the launch.

Timeline

20-27 May: release and promote video clip about the platform

6 April- 10 April: active platform promotion by the consortium

- Sending out individual emails to contacts
- Posting news on institutional websites
- Posting news in institutional newsletters

6 April 2020: platform official launch

The following actions will happen that day:

- Email sent to project mailing list
- Posts on social media platforms

01 - 06 April: social media countdown takes place

4 posts will be prepared (see Comms Content Planner) and posted on Twitter every day starting from 01 April up until the launch. Each post will contain an image and an interesting fact about the platform. Partner's role is to share these posts.

Facebook and Instagram: one D-3 and one more informative

02 April 2020 - partners receive all communication materials

- 2 factsheets (one for the general public and another one for stakeholders)
- Email template
- News example for institutional websites
- Images to use during the campaign
- Social media posts
- A short clip will be made by beginning of May

2. Textual factsheet for stakeholders

CITIZEN SCIENCE

Citizen science actively involves the public in scientific research at any stage of the research process: from the defining of research questions, to the creation and collection of scientific data and their analysis. Citizen science generates new knowledge or understanding, and thus has the potential to bring together science, policy makers, and society as a whole in an impactful way. As a core dimension of Open Science, it opens up the opportunity for all members of society to take an active role in research, innovation and the development of evidence-based policy, at local, national and EU levels.

EU-Citizen.Science: The platform for citizen science

[EU-Citizen.Science](#) is *the* digital platform for anyone interested in citizen science. It gathers best practice resources from the community for initiating, planning and executing citizen science projects, and showcases a wide range of citizen science projects to learn from, collaborate with, or participate in. Future releases of the platform will include training materials and community discussion forums as well.

Our mission is to become the central reference point for anyone setting up or running a citizen science project - such as practitioners, researchers, educators, communities and citizens, anyone supporting the ecosystem of citizen science projects - such as policy makers and funding bodies, and anyone interested in the outcomes and impact of citizen science - such as decision makers, the press, and society as a whole. It doesn't matter if you have years of experience or are completely new to citizen science.

Browse, find and share citizen science projects

Browse and search for citizen science projects across Europe, representing a wide range of fields, stages of research, and types of tasks. Search by title or keywords, or browse by country, activity status, or topic of research - such as biology, education, and physics.

Register as a member to profile your own citizen science projects, get in touch with other project managers, and collaborate on new initiatives.

Browse, find and share citizen science resources

Whether you are a newcomer looking for an introduction to citizen science, or an experienced citizen science practitioner searching for in-depth guidance to expand your expertise, you can browse through our wide catalogue of useful resources such as guidelines, toolkits or link to databases to find what you need. Search for citizen science resources by title or keyword, or browse by language, resource type, or theme - such as engagement, communication, or data quality.

The project consortium has selected a range of great resources in ‘Our selection’ on the platform to help you get started, and the community ratings will help you find resources that other citizen science practitioners find particularly useful.

By the community, for the community

The success of the platform relies on your contribution - add your project to the list, share useful resources, rate the existing ones and exchange with others. There are many ways to get actively involved and take part in shaping the European landscape of citizen science!

Make this platform your own

In your personal area on the platform you can build your own library of resources by selecting your favourites, and keep track of interesting projects by following them. Share more information about yourself in your profile to help others in the community to find you and connect with you to compare notes, or start new collaborations.

Stay on top of the news

EU-Citizen.Science follows the latest news and trends in the citizen science field, which you'll find posted regularly on our blog, announced on the events page, and shared in our newsletter. Sign up to the newsletter <link> read the latest news on a monthly basis. You can also follow us on [Twitter](#) and [Facebook](#), or contact us directly at eucitsci@mfn.berlin.

3. Visual factsheet for the general public (3 versions)

EU-Citizen.Science
The platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources

Join the community of people interested in citizen science, to share tools and resources, project know-how and project examples for new and experienced practitioners alike!

PROJECTS
Browse and search for citizen science projects across Europe, representing a wide range of fields, stages of research, and types of tasks.
Share your own citizen science projects, get in touch with other project managers, and collaborate on new initiatives.

RESOURCES
Browse and search for a wide range of resources that are useful in various stages of planning and running citizen science projects.
Share your own resources with the community – such as tools, guidelines, policy briefs, training resources, publications, and more.

FORUMS
Have a question?
The community discussion forums that will go live with the second release of the platform (summer of 2020) will enable the community to share citizen science tips, experiences and results with each other, answer questions, and start new collaborations.

OUR PLATFORM SEARCH ENGINE
search for citizen projects, resources, tools, training and more...

Search for citizen science projects by title or keywords, or browse by country, activity status, or topic of research – such as biology, education, or physics.
Search for citizen science resources by title or keyword, or browse by language, resource type, or theme – such as engagement, communication, or data quality.

BY THE COMMUNITY, FOR THE COMMUNITY
Our mission is to become the central reference point for anyone setting up or running a citizen science project – such as practitioners, researchers, educators, communities and citizens – all sharing their know-how and experience.
It doesn't matter if you have years of experience or are completely new to citizen science. Come showcase your projects, share your best.

Help us strengthen the knowledge base for citizen science approaches across all domains of science, and further encourage the democratization of science in Europe.

Are you involved in a citizen science project? Join eu-citizen.science now.
Visit <http://eu-citizen.science>

MEET THE TEAM

Share, initiate and learn about citizen science in Europe
eu-citizen.science

THE PROJECT
EU-Citizen.Science project is made by a community of practitioners, researchers, educators, communities and citizens – all sharing their know-how and experience.
It doesn't matter if you have years of experience or are completely new to citizen science. Come showcase your projects, share your best.

THE PLATFORM
EU-Citizen.Science is an online platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources for citizen science – by the community, for the community.
The vision for the platform is to aid in the mainstreaming of citizen science, and build on the growing impact of citizens participating in research across the full range of scientific enquiry, by supporting the sharing of knowledge, know-how and experience between anyone doing or wanting to do citizen science.

OUR MISSION
is for Citizen Science to become an appreciated and widely established means for the democratization of science in Europe

OUR MAIN GOALS
CONNECT citizen science practitioners and citizen science projects across Europe.
DISSEMINATE the results of citizen science projects.
Provide useful RESOURCES for researchers, project managers and volunteers.
Contribute to the establishment of STANDARDS in the communication of citizen science projects.

ON THE PLATFORM YOU WILL FIND

- RESOURCES**
EU-citizen.science is a knowledge hub for sharing guidelines, tools, papers and useful resources for initiating and running citizen science projects.
- HELP AND ADVICE**
Discover relevant citizen science projects to learn from, and connect with other practitioners.
- TRAINING**
Find useful training and capacity building resources and upcoming citizen science events to meet other practitioners in person.
- COMMUNITY**
Join the community on the platform, share your knowledge and tips and join new collaborations with fellow practitioners – new and experienced alike.

MEET THE TEAM

Are you involved in a citizen science project? Join eu-citizen.science now.
Visit <http://eu-citizen.science>

Share, innovate and learn about citizen science in Europe

eu-citizen.science

THE PROJECT

The EU Citizen Science project is building the world's largest platform for citizen science in Europe. It will be a place on where most of research-related citizen science, including tools and guidelines, have already been created.

The aim of the citizen science knowledge created in Europe is to give everyone access to citizen science and to make it more popular. It will also increase the number of researchers in citizen science to work more and get involved.

THE PLATFORM

EU Citizen Science is an online platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources for citizen science by the community for the community.

The vision for the platform is to add to the engagement of citizen science and build on the growing number of citizens participating in research projects as full stages of research inquiry by supporting the sharing of knowledge, techniques and experience between people doing or wanting to do citizen science.

Are you involved in a citizen science project? Join eu-citizen.science now.
 Visit <http://eu-citizen.science>

ON THE PLATFORM YOU WILL FIND

- RESOURCES**
EU Citizen Science is a knowledge hub for sharing guidelines, tools, papers and other resources for initiating and running citizen science projects.
- HELP AND ADVICE**
Discover relevant citizen science projects to learn from and connect with other practitioners.
- TRAINING**
EU Citizen Science is building resources and growing citizen science events to meet other practitioners in person.
- COMMUNITY**
Join the community in the forums, share knowledge and tips and can use collaboration with fellow practitioners near and international sites.

OUR MISSION

is for Citizen Science to become an appreciated and widely established means for the democratization of science in Europe

OUR MAIN GOALS

- CONNECT** citizen science practitioners and citizen science projects across Europe.
- DISSEMINATE** the results of citizen science projects.
- Provide useful **RESOURCES** for researchers, project managers and volunteers.
- Contribute to the establishment of **STANDARDS** in the communication of citizen science projects.

COORDINATE

The project will coordinate citizen science actions in Europe to share and cross-fertilise knowledge.

ENGAGE

The project will engage with stakeholders to ensure that the platform and its content meet their needs.

CREATE

The project will create and populate an online platform, which will be developed over three years (2017-21).

Meet the team

The EU Citizen Science consortium consists of 14 partners and 9 third parties from across 14 European member states, as well as other project supporters.

Are you involved in a citizen science project? Join eu-citizen.science now.
 Visit <http://eu-citizen.science>

4. Personal email template

Dear **NAME**,

I am writing to you today about the new EU-Citizen.Science platform. You might have heard about its launch through social media or other channels, but I find it important to personally introduce the platform to you. We really want this platform to become the place-to-go for citizen science in Europe, the first online resource that comes to mind, the most comprehensive collection of good quality projects, guidelines and other resources.

None of this is possible without the active involvement of the citizen science community. That is why I would like to invite you to [explore the platform](#) – search for projects, browse and rate existing resources, and while we are all working from home, to take the time to share any resource you find particularly useful, by signing up and creating a profile for it on the platform.

Considering the current complex situation as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, we have flagged citizen science projects that can be joined while staying at home or that are particularly useful to be used at home. We hope to make this list grow in the upcoming days and weeks with the contributions of the community.

In our next release over the summer we will be adding features such as a community discussion forum and training resources.

If you have any questions or suggestions about the platform, please don't hesitate to get in touch. I will be your personal contact for the platform and if you like, I will keep you updated on any major updates or events.

Best wishes,

YOUR NAME

5. Template for article/blog to be published on an organisational website

The European citizen science platform is now live

We are pleased to announce- *the* platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources for citizen science. Our project consortium of 14 partners and 9 third parties from across 14 European member states, of which **YOUR NAME** is a member, have been working together to build this reference point for citizen science participants, practitioners, researchers, policy makers and society across Europe.

We hope that this online sharing and learning space will transform the way citizen science projects are conceived and developed - encouraging and supporting citizen science initiatives, bringing the community together, and jointly advancing the role and recognition of citizen science in the European context.

Our mission is to become the central reference point for anyone setting up or running a citizen science project - such as practitioners, researchers, educators, communities and citizens, anyone supporting the ecosystem of citizen science projects - such as policy makers and funding bodies, and anyone interested in the outcomes and impact of citizen science - such as decision makers, the press, and society as a whole.

It doesn't matter if you have years of experience or are completely new to citizen science.

Anyone interested in citizen science can:

- Search for citizen science projects by title or keywords, or browse by country, activity status, or topic of research - such as biology, education, or physics.
- Browse and search for a wide range of resources that are useful in various stages of planning and running citizen science projects.
- Build your own library of resources in your personal area on the platform by selecting your favourites
- Keep track of interesting projects by following them.

- Sign up to become a member of the community, to rate resources comment on their use in practice.
- Share more information about yourself in your profile to help others in the community to find you and connect with you to compare notes, or start new collaborations.
- Share your own citizen science projects, get in touch with other project managers, and collaborate on new initiatives
- Share your own resources with the community – such as tools, guidelines, policy briefs, training resources, publications, and more

In our next release over the summer we will be adding features such as a community discussion forum and training resources. Do let us know what else you would like to see on the platform!

By the community, for the community

The success of the platform relies on your contribution - please join us as a member of this community, share your own best practice citizen science resources, and profile the citizen science projects that you have been involved with - past and present.

We welcome your thoughts and feedback - please don't hesitate to contact us here, or reach out to the platform consortium directly at eucitsci@mf.n.berlin.

Citizen science in times of the COVID-19 virus

We are all facing the challenges of the current complex situation as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. We hope that you and your loved ones are healthy and safe at this time. While many of us are under coronavirus lockdown, there is more than ever a strong need for high quality online resources and activities that can be used or done from home.

In EU-Citizen.Science we have flagged for you citizen science projects that you can join while staying at home, that are particularly useful to be used at home, with your family members, or within your virtual training or community activities. We count on your help to make this list grow in the upcoming days and weeks. On the EU-Citizen.Science platform you can also find a blogpost providing a list of resources related to the current COVID19 pandemic, as well as two projects specifically on helping researchers studying the COVID-19 spread.

6. Overview of the communication campaign on social media

Network	Time	Content Type	Copy	Notes
WEEK -1: WEDNESDAY, 25/03				
FACEBOOK	9:00 AM	Countdown 4	<p>What would you want to see on a new #CitizenScience platform? 🤖</p> <p>Get ready, because the EU-Citizen.Science platform will be launched in few days! 📅</p>	saved in Hootsuit, needs tagging of partners
TWITTER	9:00 AM	Countdown 4	<p>What would you want to see on a new #CitizenScience platform? 🤖</p> <p>Get ready, because the EU-Citizen.Science platform will be launched in few days! 📅</p>	Twitter will have a post everyday, the other platforms only one more
	1:00 PM	Other CS news		
INSTAGRAM	9:00 AM	Countdown 4	<p>What would you want to see on a new #CitizenScience platform? 🤖</p> <p>Get ready, because the EU-Citizen.Science platform will be launched in few days! 📅</p>	
WEEK -1: THURSDAY, 26/03				
FACEBOOK				
TWITTER	9:00 AM	Countdown 3	<p>In the first episode of "What will you find on EU-Citizen.Science"... 📺</p> <p>Did you say #CitizenScience projects? 🔍</p> <p>Get ready to browse, find and share citizen science projects across Europe</p>	
	1:00 PM	Other CS news		
INSTAGRAM				
WEEK -1: FRIDAY, 27/03				
FACEBOOK	9:00 AM	Countdown 2		

TWITTER	9:00 AM	Countdown 2	<p>In the second episode of "What will you find on EU-Citizen.Science "... 📺</p> <p>Browse through a great #CitizenScience resource library 📖</p> <p>A rich list of guidelines, tools, materials and other resources for citizen science projects - come share yours too!</p>	
	1:00 PM	Other CS news		
INSTAGRAM	9:00 AM	Countdown 2		
			WEEK 1: MONDAY, 30/03	
FACEBOOK				
TWITTER	9:00 AM	Countdown 1	<p>In the last episode of "What will you find on EU-Citizen.Science "... 📺</p> <p>Brace yourself, this #CitizenScience platform will be YOUR platform! 📺</p> <p>Share your project, suggest or rate resources, and build your own profile to exchange with other #CitSci lovers</p>	
	3:00 PM	Other CS news	And here it is! the EU-Citizen.Science platform for sharing #citizenscience projects and resources - come check it out, and add your own! ➡ http://eu-citizen.science/	
INSTAGRAM				
			WEEK 1: TUESDAY, 31/03	
FACEBOOK	9:00 AM	Launch	<p>Welcome to EU-Citizen.Science, the European platform for #CitizenScience!</p> <p>Finding new projects, quality resources or even keeping up with the latest news, this website is THE place to be for Citizen Science in Europe eu</p> <p>➡ http://eu-citizen.science/</p>	saved in hootsuite, paid promotion on social media
TWITTER	9:00 AM	Launch		
	1:00 PM	Other CS news		
INSTAGRAM	9:00 AM	Launch		

7. Selection of pictures to use as illustrations

The following pictures were available to partners to use, with the appropriate credits.

Pictures	Credits
	Credits_ RBINS - Bioblitz Leopold Park
	Credits_ RBINS Phasma Meeting
	Credits_ RBINS Xperibird
	Credits_ Vetenskap _ Allmänhet - Forskarfredags
	Credits_ Vetenskap _ Allmänhet - Nyckelpigeforsoket

	<p>Credits_ Vetenskap _ Allmänhet - Nyckelpigeforsoket</p>
	<p>Credits_ Vetenskap _ Allmänhet - Nyckelpigeforsoket</p>
	<p>Credits_ Vetenskap _ Allmänhet - Nyckelpigeforsoket</p>
	<p>Credits_ Vetenskap _ Allmänhet - Nyckelpigeforsoket</p>
	<p>Credits_ Vetenskap _ Allmänhet - Nyckelpigeforsoket</p>
	<p>Credits_ Vetenskap _ Allmänhet - Nyckelpigeforsoket</p>

h. Annex 8: List of Press releases/mentions about the platform launch

Press releases/News about the launch		
Organisation	Country	URL
Observatori de la Recerca	Spain	https://observatori.iec.cat/contingut/
GUNI / Global University Network for Innovation	International	http://www.guninetwork.org/news/eu-citizenscience-has-been-launched-new-platform-cross-network-knowledge-sharing
Österreich forscht	Austria	https://www.citizen-science.at/blog/plattform-eu-citizen-science-online
APA-Science	Austria	https://science.apa.at/rubrik/kultur_und_gesellschaft/Neue_Plattform_fuer_Citizen_Science_in_Europa_gestartet/SCI_20200424_SCI39351351654307072
European Commission	International	https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/launch-eu-central-platform-citizen-science-eu-2020-apr-08_en
ECSA newsletter	International	https://us3.campaign-archive.com/?u=d21c3d318d533a1a044504214&id=c89f6d86e4
European Office of Cyprus	Cyprus	http://www.eoc.org.cy/en/index.php?id=1477
Museum für Naturkunde	Germany	https://www.museumfuernaturkunde.berlin/en/press/press-releases/european-platform-citizen-research-online
Research Professional	UK	https://www.researchprofessionalnews.com/rr-news-europe-infrastructure-2020-4-eu-opens-citizen-science-platform/
FECYT	Spain	https://www.fecyt.es/es/noticia/nace-la-plataforma-europea-de-ciencia-ciudadana-eu-citizenscience
Centre for Social Innovation (ZSI)	Austria	https://www.zsi.at/en/object/project/5183
VA	Sweden	https://v-a.se/2020/04/eu-citizen-science-new-european-portal-for-citizen-science/
European Research Area	Austria	https://era.gv.at/object/news/5252
Neth-ER	The Netherlands	https://www.neth-er.eu/nl/nieuws/Commissie-lanceert-citizen-science-platform-o

Ecsite	International	https://www.ecsite.eu/activities-and-services/news-and-publications/european-citizen-science-platform-now-live
Krajowy Punkt Kontaktowy	Poland	https://www.kpk.gov.pl/eu-citizen-science-podziel-sie-wiedza-narzedziami-i-zasobami-na-rzecz-nauki-obywatelskiej
Vitoria-Gasteiz City Council	Basque	https://blogs.vitoria-gasteiz.org/ataria/2020/04/25/eu-citizen-science/?lang=eu
fonduri-structurale.ro	Romania	https://www.fonduri-structurale.ro/stiri/23639/a-fost-lansata-platforma-digitala-eu-citizen-science-adresata-comunitatii-europene-si-internationale-de-entuziasti-in-stiinta-cetatenilor
CS-Track project	International	https://cstrack.eu/news/eu-citizen-science-platform-launched/
RBB Kutlur	Germany	https://www.rbb-online.de/rbbkultur/radio/programm/schema/sendungen/rbbkultur_am_vormittag/archiv/20200408_0905/wissen_0910.html
IDW online	Germany	https://idw-online.de/en/news744366
fisicaequimica	Portugal	http://fisicaequimica.com/2020/04/07/ciencia-cidada/
Other mentions: COVID list or other		
NEMO	The Netherland	https://www.nemokennislink.nl/publicaties/zo-kun-je-de-wetenschap-een-handje-helpen/
british ecological society	UK	https://www.britishecologicalsociety.org/10-practical-tips-for-recording-wildlife-at-home/
APRE	Italy	https://www.apre.it/covid19/citizen-science-e-covid-19-una-lista-di-risorse-disponibili/
PhDHub	International	https://phdhub.eu/our-blog/citizen-science-resources-related-to-covid-19/
SparcEurope	International	https://sparceurope.org/coronaopensciencereadsandusecases/
LegaNerd	Italy	https://leganerd.com/2020/03/30/coronavirus-i-progetti-di-citizen-science-per-aiutare-la-ricerca-da-casa/
Alfred Nobel Science Park	Sweden	http://alfrednobelsp.se/nu-stottar-vi-foretagen-pa-nya-satt-under-coronakrisen/mojligheter-och-stod/
Royal microscopical society	UK	https://www.rms.org.uk/discover-engage/primary-age-microscopy-resources.html

Schweiz Forscht	Switzerland	https://www.schweiz-forscht.ch/de/aktuell/news/item/459-citizen-science-in-zeiten-von-covid-19
CEON Otwarta Nauka	Poland	https://otwartanauka.pl/blog/1227-otwarta-nauka-w-walce-z-pandemia-koronawirusa-sars-cov-2
europedirect.gva.es	Spain	http://www.europedirect.gva.es/documents/165383013/169756865/MEDIDAS+DE+L+A+UNI%C3%93N+EUROPEA+CONTRA+EL+COVID19.pdf/d27978f8-7147-450e-a9f2-20991af2211a
Coronavirus Tech Handbook	International	https://coronavirustechhandbook.com/science
Twitter		
List of all the tweets		https://twitter.com/EUCitSciProject/timelines/1250018994767224833
Facebook		
Punto Europeo de Ciudadanía	Spain	https://www.facebook.com/PuntoEuropeodeCiudadania/photos/a.358021237646854/2923473557768263/?type=3&av=373406149450526&eav=AfYpTnYEcY9P6LALkSRNgEXTBIAMGVywNWP3p4CFfPrzIXIjSH4muxFh8zbssi6ESYQ&theater
Krajowy Punkt Kontaktowy Programów Badawczych UE	Poland	https://www.facebook.com/KPK.Polska/posts/1563843407112802?_tn_=-R
Museo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología MUNCYT	Spain	https://www.facebook.com/muncyt/posts/2872295659544145?_tn_=-R
Fedalcyta	Spain	https://www.facebook.com/Fedalcyta/posts/1552256424938670?_tn_=-R
Citizen Science/Bürgerwissenschaft Universität Salzburg	Austria	https://www.facebook.com/PLUS.citizenscience/posts/3067055040013011?_tn_=-R
Plataforma de Ciência Aberta	Portugal	https://www.facebook.com/PlataformaCienciaAberta/posts/633011897246763?_tn_=-R
SPAIN arts & culture - Belgium	Spain	https://www.facebook.com/spainartsandculturebe/photos/a.511513298969106/2809576685829411/?type=3&av=373406149450526&eav=AfZZdeSTC75r-C4vrDUyUW3arFF27RLhocFiAinRggV3qB6ClbtZCbP5XooB_8aiVo

Ecsite	International	https://www.facebook.com/EcsiteNetwork/photos/a.245929398808308/2973979039336650/?type=3&av=373406149450526&eav=AfYDlBxrSnHYqAMbo6l8FmYCL4TS3EMvcHicmUxTpJ5ULAElqMtL_XFwVAfye2tXJSM&_xts_%5Bo%5D=68.ARCKhweMV-sCkNGE_GXHlJmZrFNp8q2wBZ2PrMASaGIL-GMK4mAovbDyQxYSpJJMUoULdNcIG5TWD2XemFgh7Hp2hcCPWdmD_msdBetae3gkO65Ie5kwGAHEap09VZ2CkiImHSriqcefl_g5xBoZV_SanToAGhJehbkS9N_HBfxvNKXQBUiPUiXOO3IDsDVb_j4GTelJkNZYJ4NhqKSTVcBQEUCqhPP3RX_Ts8tqvV2eaj2Hbo7Ly8A4rQ-sHSHeUhrclIRO2MQmYyEUMgz19r1eDd43vR4Mee59rEfO4B9WN9mxijAzw69g6RvAppFtnMTIPuB&_tn_=-R
Citizen Science Zurich	Switzerland	https://www.facebook.com/CitSciZurich/posts/631793480999112?_xts_%5Bo%5D=68.ARBVOyS82EM39Jwuly8_QfbHEssXKPW952fY9Y6297YQ_zmBoqtiHsmDgreygb7p4ciGB9el7u-OGuiL3Qovxwo3Jhdk325512FmBkmrTOGEYSdz4DY_xRixR5bcO4XorELr4NoXIk6_gBdB8eJl04pkvqsIR2K6Ie2fr-1kUmwisS5VaTi-YR4mWdpcuCYra6ZP-qArAjHQg4fnEUDGrZrNlB4AEz2PPv_3hoMvaBY8k29GAEO2XwmMLP9lnesGajKS8D3y1o_gV57Yt9Ohfyl5oVhsXh6_UDmPR4_vFUQ9nT76hPVXIsPoDIknBpholjzsV26Zts_a5NNrNEBqfU7YdB5tsXJZx1_fBOs8FqsKbpgf5t8zomxWuREtrPLp5fo_TSedLgZP_UTAJUcPq-JVwa6aAKoabk-UPAZzAprisXt2kpu9rxyrtnVrUjOLupSAnaO_SmsdtLlpcm9VBw5SHP36erJTg&_tn_=-R
Zentrum für Citizen Science	Austria	https://www.facebook.com/zentrum.fuer.citizen.science/photos/a.1688267431387541/2683492135198394/?type=3&av=373406149450526&eav=AfZ3HDY7sI7FEyoWkZAdJL_I2Ln2pogIT2VqkWKkWfgCmHIRPEtsO1NMkvaNu5Gxo2I&_tn_=-R
VA	Sweden	https://www.facebook.com/vetenskapollm/posts/10157165531843603?_tn_=-R

FECYT	Spain	https://www.facebook.com/fecyt.ciencia/posts/3119114458119007?_xts__%5Bo%5D=68.ARCFWK5yKofzDHUt6CsRe7GjZw5j2CrCYfyfPkScDyhtDI7nlK_NI6Fc4bDM8s5drnaw_OQ2eiNlJC2cK4OeFOywveV9od7Mt-TiuJpio7RnMfZrDEMZgch2BFHMLx-gJO85mMcAgT4e58cQeDwBoow2IjRfGv4MrIK2fz4FJA493jBtX2QFyJ-WoNWTAlCobvD3-KPaoyMs904Oiy83xRCgn3JQZ2YKQo_zSRWBS9PsfdsM4fUd4_qGfMsDMoIYXd3cnOJO72P7Ytok_zzzabtU_rmdpMSZ2PSrKs4ieJLjVVhLnbTKP_7xnKujqdOroqdf&_tn_=-R
Bürger schaffen Wissen	Germany	https://www.facebook.com/buergerschaffenwissen/photos/a.1431531227096251/2534201260162570/?type=3&av=373406149450526&eav=AfZ50PwladRoCOVfYhW8fnZoS017KpOkWjr_ieLOZlzKVKn_WsgijPazT2vD5URiMbM&theater
Citizen Science Austria	Austria	https://www.facebook.com/csaustria/photos/a.665410106920814/2654589348002870/?type=3&av=373406149450526&eav=AfZX2aRI2JJ9B6CXmxTlSxWVCP_Rk7MweZvL-T5QT19JZiMwRjPGrLkXYxywfltUWWg&_xts__%5Bo%5D=68.ARAUbVoNlF2Ww1HjfEzeuj2aGKLyvSsc_3Bm38mlEd64lvJ81cm--bDsqInaIQ92T-Ok06gPnwArY2QFupJPSHzpl-JJALYgE22xAd8nEwpvzWIg3Fsj28m99W9Rg6zyWsnpZ9VbxRQZVf5xKeyzKlFRpBnM631EutGyDt7gR4BUD2JrQA-x7CFcK86rr2iRmcXzQ7VMTlrkwWmUibqeQXE8Tvyv7FoOclcMUm69TE8acfHXP5oX2olkdM8HoRSIoMD-ltNqiyogcw79aF7ivOvkF7LZ49xRtWUz2PeMUgKKbH4XYjukSqrGsKD8_4sUaZyC&_tn_=-R
FECYT	Spain	https://www.facebook.com/fecyt.ciencia/posts/3172138729483246?_tn_=-R

3. Project's roadmap

4. Rollup and poster stand

EU-Citizen.Science

The platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources for Citizen Science

Join the community of people interested in citizen science, to share tools and resources, project know-how and project examples for new and experienced practitioners alike!

PROJECTS

Browse and search for **citizen science projects across Europe**, representing a wide range of fields, stages of research, and types of tasks.

Share your own citizen science projects, get in touch with other project managers, and collaborate on new initiatives.

RESOURCES

Browse and search for a wide range of **resources that are useful** in various stages of planning and running citizen science projects.

Share your own resources with the community – such as tools, guidelines, policy briefs, training resources, publications, and more.

FORUMS

Have a question?

The community discussion forums enable the community to share citizen science tips, experiences and results with each other answer questions and start new collaborations.

OUR PLATFORM SEARCH ENGINE

search for citizen projects, resources, tools, training and more...

Search for citizen science projects **by title or keywords**, or **browse by country, activity status, or topic of research** – such as biology, education, or physics.

Search for citizen science resources by title or keyword, or **browse by language, resource type, or theme** – such as engagement, communication, or data quality.

BY THE COMMUNITY, FOR THE COMMUNITY

Our mission is to become the **central reference point for anyone setting up or running a citizen science project** – such as practitioners, researchers, educators, communities and citizens – all sharing their know-how and experience.

It doesn't matter if you have years of experience or are completely new to citizen science. Come showcase your projects, share your best practice resources, and **join the conversation!**

Help us **strengthen the knowledge base for citizen science** approaches across all domains of science, and further encourage the democratization of science in Europe.

Are you involved in a citizen science project?
Join eu-citizen.science now.

Visit <http://eu-citizen.science>

j. Annex 10: List of events

TBC with missing information

Date	Location	Type of Activity	Short Description	Total number of attendees
13/01/2019	Helsinki	Participation to a conference	SAPEA conference "The Future of Science Advice in Europe"	200
14/03/2019	Leiden Observatory	Participation to a conference	Citizen science and water quality	70
30/03/2019	Brussels	Participation to a workshop	Presentation about the platform at a COST workshop	12
01/04/2019	Brussel	Organisation of Workshop	'Building a community network for educators, teachers, Citizen Science practitioners and researchers on synergies between Citizen Science and Education' was organised and run by the Members the Citizen Science COST Action CA15212 Working Group 2 'Education', in collaboration with ECSA and the Project. The main goal of the workshop was to effectively and sustainably connect the diverse stakeholders in the field of Citizen Science	18
04/04/2019		Participation to a workshop	GLOBE day	70
10/04/2019	Brussels	Organisation of Workshop	EU-Citizen.Science and Citizen Science Cost Action CA15212 joint workshop: Co-creating the EU platform for citizen science	20

09/05/2019	Örebro	Participation to a conference	Poster. Raising awareness of CS and of project at the HSS2019 conference.	200
18/05/2019	Leiden Observatory	Participation to a workshop	Museum Night Leiden. At the Leiden Observatory we presented several CS projects and had a booth about CS in general and the CS Lab	250
24/05/2019	Zurich	Participation to a workshop	EPA Network – Interest Group on Citizen Science Fourth Meeting	50
28/05/2019		Participation to a workshop	Democratic Innovations in Europe and Western Balkans Grassroots Initiatives; organisers asked for an input on European Citizen Science activities	15
04/06/2019	Cesis	Participation to a conference	Fifth Citizen Science Cost Action MC and WG Meeting - Citizen Science Strategies in Europe	100
07/06/2019	Copenhagen	Participation to a conference	Presentation at the Project Showcase session of the Ecsite Conference	40
12/06/2019	Leiden Observatory	Participation to a workshop	CS Psychology lab	10
15/06/2019	Berlin	Participation to a workshop	Lange Nacht der Wissenschaften	15
17/06/2019	Leiden Observatory	Participation to a workshop	Special evening for inhabitants of city of Leiden	30
25/06/2019	Leiden Observatory	Participation to a workshop	At the 'knowledge day' for employees of the local government 2 CS projects were presented that were set up with their funding to two groups of around 25 employees to inform them and receive feedback.	50
26/06/2019	Austria	Participation to a conference	Austrian Citizen Science Conference	150
28/06/2019	The Netherlands	Participation to a conference	Meeting for health professionals about potentials of CS by ZonMw (the organization that funds research in health in the Netherlands)	50

02/07/2019	The Netherlands	Participation to a workshop	Participation in international event of WWF-IUCN. Poster presentation by Matthijs and plenary presentation by Margaret.	60
03/09/2019	Brussels	Participation to a workshop	GROW Policy Workshop - Observatory Policy Interface workshop of the GROW Observatory, H2020 project	100
18/09/2019	Porto, Portugal	Participation to a conference	Speaker at a workshop at the Open Science Fair Conference on "towards-an-alliance-of-citizen-science-in-europe" (https://www.opensciencefair.eu/workshops-2019/towards-an-alliance-of-citizen-science-in-europe)	50
27/09/2019	Gothenburg	Trade fair	Science café. Raising awareness of CS and of the project at the Gothenburg Book Fair.	20
08/10/2019	Stockholm	Organisation of Conference	Annual VA conference. On how to involve the general public in research. Creating engagement for CS and the project.	145
09/10/2019	Brussels	Participation to a conference	European Week of Regions and Cities	65
24/10/2019	Lisbon, Portugal	Participation to a conference	Series of talks at the 2nd Portuguese Citizen Science Meeting	210
30/10/2019	Barca D'Alva, Portugal	Organisation of Workshop	Organization of monthly citizen science activities to monitor the water quality of the Douro river (as part of the Drinkable Rivers project, https://drinkablerivers.org/), in collaboration with schools, citizens and policy makers	50
12/12/2019	Brussels	Participation to a workshop	HORIZON 2020 CITIZEN SCIENCE CLUSTER MEETING - Organized by REA B5 – Spreading excellence and Widening participation & Science with and for Society	50
09/03/2020	Berlin, MFN	Organisation of Workshop		20

11/03/2020	Berlin, OpenScienceCnferenc e	Participation to a conference		200
05/05/2020	Vienna, Austria	Participation to a conference	The Citizen Science Network Austria is organising the 6th Austrian Citizen Science Conference in 2020. The annual conference on Citizen Science, the active participation of citizens in scientific projects, is held at a different location and by a different institution every year. In 2020, the University of Vienna will organise this transdisciplinary conference under the motto "Citizen Science: Demand and Significance" from 6-8 May 2020 on the campus in the heart of Vienna. Following the conference, the University of Vienna will also dedicate the Long Night of Research 2020 on 8 May to the involvement of citizens in research projects.	15
04/06/2020	Online	Participation to a conference	Moderator of the debate organized within the SciComPt 2020 Online Conference, entitled: "EU-Citizen.Science - platform for Citizen Science", to discuss: What resources, tools and training modules does the community consider most relevant ?; What is the importance of sharing experiences between participants?.	190
22/09/2020	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Final workshop of a local CS project, where the platform was promoted via trailer and a presentation about its possibilities and opportunities	26
29/09/2020	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Final event of a local CS project, where the platform was promoted via trailer and a presentation about its possibilities and opportunities	30

29/09/2020	Online	Organisation of Workshop	What is Open Science to me? Including session on citizen science (what is, and how to run a successful project)	30
15/10/2020	Online	Organisation of Conference	Speaker at the CS SDG 2020 Conference. Oral communication focused on the project: "Drinkable Rivers - Citizen Science as a tool for the involvement of the local community in monitoring water quality of the Douro River"	266
21/10/2020	Online	Participation to a conference	Presentation of the ECSA Principles, Characteristics, and EU-Citizen.Science platform at the Dutch Design Week, Embassy of Health	200
03/11/2020	Online	Participation to a conference	Presentation of the ECSA Principles, Characteristics, and EU-Citizen.Science platform at the first Citizen Science Lab Webinar	50
04/11/2020	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Presentation of EU-Citizen.Science platform and training resources available	8
12/11/2020	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Presentation of EU-Citizen.Science platform and training resources available	10
12/11/2020	Online	Participation to a workshop	Presentation of the ECSA Principles, Characteristics, and EU-Citizen.Science platform at the first Citizen Science Lab Webinar	35
12/11/2020	online	Organisation of Workshop	Webinar about the characteristics of CS	40
17/11/2020	online	Participation to a workshop	Web conference for young people about air quality for the Netherlands	20
20/11/2020	online	Participation to a conference	Conference on national level about CS with special attention to health	200
24/11/2020	online	Participation to a workshop	ECSA WG Air Quality: European Clean Air 2020 Webinar. Sharing best practices on engaging with citizens in air quality monitoring	40

27/11/2020	Online	Brokerage event	https://www.tcd.ie/research/start/citizen-science.php	30
08/12/2020	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Making CS – challenges, drivers and benefits. Workshop for researchers.	30
19/01/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Workshop for BOKU researchers on how to integrate citizen science in their research	10
21/01/2021	Online	Participation to a workshop	Presentation at the Citizen Science SwafS workshop	69
26/01/2021	Online	Participation to a workshop	Course for university students at the University of Salzburg	50
09/02/2021	Online	Activities jointly with other EU projects	Presentation of the platform in the Kick-off meeting of the YouCount project	72
17/02/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Public workshop on citizen science (Hungarian)	25
18/03/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Workshop/presentation of the platform to a group of museum employees at RBINS	20
25/03/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Workshop for the funding programme Top Citizen Science by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	25
14/04/2021	Online	Organisation of Conference	Forum for Science Communication. Including a session on CS ("citizen science – the democratization of science?")	40
19/04/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Presentation of the platform and personas exercise in the context of an ECSA training for an Ukrainian NGO	15
06/05/2021	Online	Participation to a conference	HSS2021 conference. Session "Citizen science – collaboration for all", introducing CS and the platform	20
09/05/2021	Rome	Training	Training event for school teachers	25
12/05/2021	Online	Participation to a conference	Participation at a conference (Hungarian)	7
20/05/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Citizen science and collaboration in research – promoting CS and the platform	20

21/05/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Creating awareness about CS and the platform	25
21/05/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Presenting CS and promoting the EU-CS portal, webinar.	30
26/05/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Presentation of the platform in a workshop on citizen science organised for the ROSiE consortium	20
17/06/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Promotion of platform	20
21/06/2021	Online	Organisation of Conference	Ecsite workroom	43
25/06/2021	Online	Participation to a conference	Speaker at the SciComPt 2021 Online Conference. Oral communication focused on online training for the implementation of citizen science projects in school practices	263
25/06/2021	Online	Participation to a conference	Speaker at the SciComPt 2021 Online Conference. Oral communication focused on citizen science as a tool for creating scientific knowledge and involve communities - the case of water monitoring in Figueira de Castelo Rodrigo	263
01/07/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Presentation of the platform in a workshop at the Living Knowledge Festival	6
11/09/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Science festival online workshop about citizen science, including the portal	40
15/09/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	CS – challenges, drivers and benefits. Inspirational workshop for researchers.	15
21/09/2021	Online	Participation to a workshop	Presentation of the platform within the presentation “Our world – our goals: Citizen Science for the Sustainable Development Goals” in the webinar Series “Transforming our World: Participatory-driven approaches and the Sustainable Development Goals”	20

04/10/2021	Online	Participation to a workshop	Presentation of the platform (platform tour) and Q&A for DZNE in Rostock	6
04/10/2021	Online	Participation to a workshop	Presentation given for the DZNE-Rostock	5
05/10/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	"Should/can everyone participate in science?" about citizen science, promoting the platform	35
09/10/2021	Online	Participation to a conference	Panel at the the First Steps 2021 International exchange	30
18/10/2021	Geneva	Participation to a conference	MoP7 of the Aarhus convention	200
27/10/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Final launch of the platform event "What's new in citizen science training: from open science to public engagement" + presentation of the platform	90
30/10/2021	Urania, Berlin	Trade fair	Presentation of the platform at the "Tabula rasa – Wissenschaft zum Anfassen" forum/fair in Berlin	10
09/11/2021	Online	Participation to a workshop	Presentation of the platform given at the EPAnet Interest Group CS	8
09/11/2021	Online	Participation to a workshop	Presentation given at the EPAnet Interest Group CS	10
11/11/2021	Grosseto (Italy)	Organisation of Conference	Citizen Science Italia National event	1585
11/11/2021	Online	Participation to a conference	Presentation given at the Italian Citizen Science Conference	1500
12/11/2021	Grosseto (Italy)	Organisation of Conference	Citizen Science Italia National event	1600
18/11/2021	University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna	Organisation of Workshop	promoting platform	10
22/11/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	promoting platform and final event	8

24/11/2021	Online	Participation to a conference	Presentation of the platform at the Final Conference of the project jointly organized with Action project	150
24/11/2021	Online	Organisation of Conference	Final Conference of the project jointly organized with Action project	405
25/11/2021	Online, Porto, Braga, Faro, Coimbra, Almada, Covilhã, Santarém, Oeiras	Organisation of Conference	Organization of the Portuguese's National Meeting for Citizen Science	260
25/11/2021	Covilhã	Participation to a conference	Speaker at the Portuguese's National Meeting for Citizen Science. Oral communication focused on the project: "Drinkable Rivers - Citizen science and water quality of the Douro River"	260
26/11/2021	University of Zurich	Organisation of Workshop	promoting platform	15
03/12/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Presentation of the work done in EU-Citizen.Science at the ECSA annual general meeting	60
06/12/2021	Online	Participation to a workshop	Promoting CS, including EU-CS courses	12
08/12/2021	The Swedish Museum of Natural History	Organisation of Conference	Sweden's first national conference on CS. On-site conference with Swedish researchers, policymakers, project coordinators, etc. Keynote by Silke Voigt-Heucke.	60
18/12/2021	Online	Organisation of Workshop	Internal workshop for experts on citizen science	7
	Online	Participation to a workshop	Speaker at the SciComPt 2020 Online Conference. Oral communication focused on the project: "Drinkable Rivers - Citizen science and water quality of the Douro River"	266

k. Annex II: Final event programme

“The future of citizen science: sharing experiences from the European community” 24-25 November 2021

PROGRAMME

Day one 24 November 2021

11.00-11:20 Welcome and opening

11.20 - 11.30 The future of citizen science in Horizon Europe - Patrick Brenier, European Commission

11.30 - 11:45 ACTION: lessons learned and way ahead - Elena Simperl, King's College London

11:45 - 12:00 EU-Citizen.Science: the European knowledge platform for citizen science - Silke Voigt-Heucke and Antonella Radicchi, Museum für Naturkunde Berlin

12:00 -13:00 Sharing knowledge for empowering citizen science

This session presents training resources and materials on citizen science followed by a roundtable on how their legacy can be sustained long-term. - Muki Haklay (UCL), Claudia Fabó Cartas, (ECSA), Gefion Thuermer (KCL), Oscar Corcho (UPM), Sven Schade (JRC), Linden Farrer (EC)

13.00 - 14:00 Lunch in a social room

Let's have lunch and a chat together

13:00 - 14:00 Network with peers

Head to the networking area to be matched with someone for a 3 minute chat

14:00 - 15:00 Discover our exhibition of citizen science projects and initiatives

Head to the expo section

15:00 - 15:30 Citizen science for societal transformation

Sharing of success stories on how citizen science can tackle societal issues such as climate change, the transition towards carbon-neutral cities, spreading of scientific culture and empowering communities - Dilek Fraisl (IIASA), James Pickstone (The Restart Project), Marc Aguilar (Bit Lab Cultural), Sílvia Tavares (Ocean Alive)

Sessions: 15.30 -16.00 Parallel session: "Revealing what companies hide: why our gadgets break and what that means for the planet".

James Pickstone - The Restart Project

Sessions: 15.30 -16.00 Parallel session: "Noise maps: empowering citizens to redesign their soundscapes"

Marc Aguilar - Bit Lab Cultural

Sessions: 15.30 -16.00 Parallel session: Parallel session: "Water sentinels: citizen-science for water quality"

Sílvia Tavares - Ocean Alive

16:00 - 16:20 Highlights of the discussions and QA with speakers

16:20 - 16:30 Wrap-up of the day

Day two 25 November 2021

10:00 - 10:10 Welcome and opening of day two

10:10 - 10:30 "Citizen and societal engagement: A policy and programme priority for the European Commission" - including time for Q&A - Linden Farrer, European Commission

10:30 - 11:10 The added value of citizen science

How do you assess the impact of citizen science projects and initiatives? Methodologies and tools from ACTION and EU-Citizen.Science - Antonella Passani (T6 Ecosystems), Anelli Janssen (DRIFT), Barbara Kieslinger (ZSI), Teresa Schafer (ZSI)

11:10 - 11:30 Coffee break in a social room

11:30 - 12:00 Tour of Europe: reflections on citizen science nationally

Representatives from 7 European countries share their experience of having been involved in the EU-Citizen.Science project, what it has meant for them, lessons learnt, and current and future developments for citizen science in their countries.

12:00-12:40 Fishbowl: Outlook into the future

Silke Voigt-Heucke (MfN), Dorte Riemenschneider (ECSA), Maria Inês Vicente (Município de Figueira de Castelo Rodrigo - Portugal, Leiden University - The Netherlands) (to be confirmed), Francisco Sanz (Ibercivis), Gefion Thuermer (KCL), Antonella Passani (T6 Ecosystems), Kat Austen (IGB Berlin)

1. Annex 12: Workroom programme

EU-Citizen.Science Workroom: Citizen Science Clinic

DAY 1: Inspiring stories

For this introductory session, we will take inspiration from Anne Bowser, Director of Innovation at the Woodrow Wilson International Center for Scholars where she explores the challenge of making science better, and technology more equitable. Following her keynote, participants will discover successful citizen science projects delivering impact be it societal, scientific or political. Participants will then be split into small groups to learn more about one of the 4 projects presented.

PROGRAMME OVERVIEW

15:00 Introductions and icebreakers

15:15 Keynote from Anne Bowser, Director of Innovation at the [Wilson Center, Washington, DC](#) followed by QA

15:45 Two presentations on societal and scientific impact:

- Guillem Camprodon from [Making sense](#): Societal impact
- Aitana Oltra from [Mosquito Alert](#): Scientific impact

16:00 In depth-discussion in small groups

16:15 Break

16:20 Two policy impact presentations:

- Dilek Fraisl from [IIASA](#): Citizen science and the SDGs
- Anna Berti Suman from [Tilburg Institute for Law, Technology, and Society](#): Political impact

16:35 Small group discussions

16:50 Wrap-up

DAY 2: Impact assessment frameworks

During this second session, participants will dig into envisioning the impact their projects could make. In order to do so, they will be presented with 3 existing citizen science impact assessment frameworks that have recently been developed. Following the presentations, they will be split into groups to see how the frameworks work in practice and how they could be applied to their own citizen science projects.

PROGRAMME OVERVIEW

15:00 Introductions and icebreakers

15:15 Presentation of the [EU-Citizen.Science](#) platform

15:20 Panel of different projects that have developed frameworks for impact assessment:

- Barbara Kieslinger from [ZSI](#)
- Antonella Passani from [Action](#)
- Stephen Parkinson from [MICS](#)

16:00 Practical workshops on the implementation of these frameworks

16:45 Wrap-up

DAY 3: Financial sustainability

Sustainability is usually one of the key concerns for many projects, not less citizen science ones. In this last session, participants will learn about existing funding opportunities for citizen science projects at European level. Following that they will hear from three different initiatives on how they made their initial projects financially viable. Finally, working in pairs, participants will have to think about their own projects and their economic sustainability.

PROGRAMME OVERVIEW

15:00 Introductions and icebreakers

15:15 Presentation from Linden Farrer from the [European Commission](#) on the financial options for Citizen Science projects in Horizon Europe

15:50 Presentation of business model types that can be considered to sustain citizen science initiatives:

- Rosa Arias ([Science for Change](#)): Creating a start-up - a path towards sustainability of CS projects
- Norbert Steinhaus ([Bonn Science Shop](#)): sustainability of Citizen Science through science shops
- Marco Sebastianelli ([Plusvalue](#)) - impact investing and links with citizen science

16:25 Create your own sustainable business model, adapted to your project

16:50 Wrap-up

m. Annex 13: Satisfactory responses workroom

14 workroom participants responded to the feedback form. They were asked to rate the following propositions:

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
The content of the Workroom I attended was interesting.	8	5	1	0	0
The Workroom was sufficiently interactive	9	3	1	1	0
The content of the Workroom I attended was well presented	8	5	0	0	0
The content of the Workroom I attended was relevant to my work	6	5	2	0	0
The Workroom met my expectations	7	5	0	1	0
Regarding the communication of the Workroom, did you receive enough information before the sessions started?	6	4	2	1	0
Regarding the communication of the Workroom, did you receive enough information during the series?	9	3	1	0	0

In a second time, a few open questions have been used to collect their opinions and suggestions

What inspired you to register for this Workroom?

- Interested in knowing more about CS
- Interest in the topic
- To know more about citizen science impact and financial sustainability
- In my working environment citizen science is taken too lightly, like an add-on
- It was nice to have a whole series about these topics, which are of concern for many CS projects.
- The opportunity to meet and discuss citizen science projects with a diverse and global cohort.
- topic and format
- I will work soon on a citizen science project
- My interest in CS
- I am new in the field and I would like to find information
- Citizen science plays a growing role in Science Centers

What did you like about the EU Citizen Science Workroom series as a whole?

- The discussions
- Interactive approach, various speakers
- Very interesting, easy to follow and interactive
- I enjoyed a lot the range of experiences and specializations
- Getting to know new approaches and methods
- The series is interactive and supportive, I hope to join more.
- short speeches, small groups
- The richness of the speakers
- Topics, the way they were presented
- That the same principles applied and detected to all the presentations, so I was able to understand
- Good presenters

Which moments were to you the most valuable?

- Discussions
- chatting to others in small groups.
- I liked the metadata approach
- The ice breakers and the break out sessions
- All, I enjoyed the key presentations, the breakout rooms, and the host's little activities to get everyone thinking.
- work in small groups (but VERY short)
- The presentations of other projects + icebreakers
- Interactive activities
- All the same
- The presentations (as opposed to the interactive parts of the sessions)

Please leave any other general feedback for us here - thank you!

- Thanks for organising! And happy summer :-)
- Very interesting and well managed! Thanks!
- It was a great experience, sure I am going to share and apply in the next future
- Thanks for your effort! Have a great summer!
- Thank you so much! Great diverse group of presenters, lovely!
- Thank you to organizers, was great !!!
- I received no clear info before the event (about agenda and hour starting meeting); maybe it's better to send an email a few days before the event (with all the info useful to join it) as a reminder for the audience
- ok!
- The workroom did not meet my expectations because it was about citizen science as such. There are many events and talks about citizen science out there. What I expect from ECSITE is a focus on what citizen science can do for or in science centers/museums.

n. Annex 14: Visual identity

Main logo

The main logo consists of various colours. One red connection and two green connections accompanied by the blue circles.

eu-citizen.science

p4 eu-citizen.science
visual identity guidelines

Logo Lockup

the margins of the logo are of the same width and height as the biggest circle

p5 eu-citizen.science
visual identity guidelines

Main logo

Variations
If (visually) needed the main logo can be used in different colors. However, the connected circles are never the same color.

p6 eu-citizen.science
visual identity guidelines

Main logo

Colour
When the logo is used in colour the wordmark is always blue. When used in black or white the whole logo is monocoloured.

p7 eu-citizen.science
visual identity guidelines

Main logo

Colour
The multi coloured logo can only be used on a white background. When the logo needs to be used on a coloured background you can use blue, or black.

p8 eu-citizen.science
visual identity guidelines

Secondary horizontal logo

The horizontal logo can only be used in one or two colours. The text is either black or blue. The biggest circle is always the same size as the 'o' from the wordmark.

p9 eu-citizen.science
visual identity guidelines

Logo Lockup

the margins of the logo are of the same width and height as the biggest circle

p10 eu-citizen.science visual identity guidelines

Secondary horizontal logo

The horizontal logo can only be used in one or two colours. The text is either black or blue. The biggest circle is always the same size as the 'o' from the wordmark.

p11 eu-citizen.science visual identity guidelines

2. Colour

Palette

The colour palette consists of three main, primary colours. Black and white are free to use.

Combinations

3. Typography

Route 5
Typography

Primary
Mark Pro is a contemporary slightly rounded font with an approachable feel.

Mark Pro ^{bold}

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii
Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

p16 eric liebermann
visual identity guidelines

Route 5
Typography

Secondary
Cormorant Garamond is a outspoken serif font that works well in contrast with the rounded Mark Pro. It has a professional and sophisticated feel. It is a free to use Google font.

Cormorant Garamond Regular

Cormorant Garamond Medium

Cormorant Garamond Semibold

ABCDEFGHIJK
LMNOPQRSTU
VWXYZ. 012345
6789 ! ? /) >

ABCDEFGHIJK
LMNOPQRSTU
VWXYZ. 012345
6789 ! ? /) >

ABCDEFGHIJK
LMNOPQRSTU
VWXYZ. 012345
6789 ! ? /) >

abcdefghijklm
nopqrstuvwxyz

Disruptive
technology

Social
Impact

p17 eric liebermann
visual identity guidelines

a b c

In use

Example of typographic styles in use

p19 eu-citizen.science visual identity guidelines

Coordinate, Engage & Create

Ecite is the European network of science centres and museums which is based in Brussels. We are currently looking for designers to come up with a visual identity and a set of communication tools for our new EU funded project.

The EU-Citizen.Science project will establish a community hub for high quality citizen science exchange and learning in order to consolidate and centralise the citizen science knowledge base in Europe. For more information about the project please read the information in the Annex.

Header
Mark pro sold

Ecite is the European network of science centres and museums which is based in Brussels. We are currently looking for designers to come up with a visual identity and a set of communication tools for our new EU funded project.

Ecite.net
Citizen Science

In use

Example of typographic styles in use in colour that are allowed

p20 eu-citizen.science visual identity guidelines

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Ecite is the European network of science centres and museums which is based in Brussels. We are currently looking for designers to come up with a visual identity and a set of communication tools for our new EU funded project.

In use

Example of typographic styles in use in colour that are NOT allowed

p21 eu-citizen.science visual identity guidelines

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4. Photography

Photography

We would like to use imagery that is both figurative and abstract at the same time. They can show surprising forms that are shaped by natural and organic objects or places.

p23 eu-citizen.science visual identity guidelines

o. Annex 15: List of mini teasers

Micro-teaser	Action promoted	Thumbnail	Link
Microteaser 1: Sign up!	Creating an account		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=B9O4eJjAJs&list=PLB6IBD9OG9pD6OLR2cPVAjYEUmftsW98N&index=3
Microteaser 2: About forums	Using the forums section		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9NwyUxD_vuU&list=PLB6IBD9OG9pD6OLR2cPVAjYEUmftsW98N&index=4
Micro teaser 3: Library	Saving a project in the library		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=27edescD_Bg&list=PLB6IBD9OG9pD6OLR2cPVAjYEUmftsW98N&index=10
Micro teaser 4: Create your organisation's profile	Create an organisational profile		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9aoklY8uvkM&list=PLB6IBD9OG9pD6OLR2cPVAjYEUmftsW98N&index=5

<p>Micro teaser 5: Do a review</p>	<p>Rating and reviewing projects</p>		<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=on5a2UMI094&list=PLB6IBD9OG9pD6OLR2cPVAjYEUmftsW98N&index=9</p>
<p>Micro teaser 6: Golden selection</p>	<p>Explaining the “gold star selection”</p>		<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=THp46l3g8oc&list=PLB6IBD9OG9pD6OLR2cPVAjYEUmftsW98N&index=8</p>
<p>Micro teaser 7: How to add your own project</p>	<p>Submitting a project on the platform</p>		<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wJ8X2Q4iEJw&list=PLB6IBD9OG9pD6OLR2cPVAjYEUmftsW98N&index=7</p>
<p>Micro teaser 8: How to add your own resources</p>	<p>Submitting a resource</p>		<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pAiOuDprtp8&list=PLB6IBD9OG9pD6OLR2cPVAjYEUmftsW98N&index=6</p>